

mates

Maritime Alliance for fostering the
European Blue Economy through a
Marine Technology Skilling Strategy

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Foresight scenarios
identifying future skills
needs and trends [January
2020]

Work Package 2. Strategy baseline: identification of present and future skills' needs

Deliverable 2.3: Foresight Scenarios identifying Future Skills and Trends

This report was developed through the EC-funded Erasmus+ project **MATES: Maritime Alliance for fostering the European Blue Economy through a Marine Technology Skilling Strategy**.

The objective of the project is to develop a skills strategy that addresses the main drivers of change in maritime industry, in particular shipbuilding and offshore renewable energy. Both sectors are strongly linked and require new capacities to succeed in an increasingly digital, green and knowledge- driven economy.

Duration: January 2018 - December 2021 (48 months)

More information on the project is available at www.projectmates.eu.

Document information	
Short description	This document, (MATES deliverable D2.3 “Foresight scenarios identifying future skills needs and trends”) deals with the identification and analysis of emerging trends with respect to new technologies, new skills, training programs and other associated parameters (i.e. emerging jobs, affected ages and genders etc.). Based on a critical review, mobilization of experts and a Delphi exercise, future scenarios on skills and competences, as well as gaps in the current and foreseen levels sectors at the short, mid and long-term are described.
Next steps	This document will contribute to the proposal of a set of action lines addressing main skills needs expected in the future scenarios. It will be analysed together with the deliverables produced in WP1 and WP2, namely the D1.2 “State of the Art Compilation” and the D2.1 “Baseline Report on present skills needs in shipbuilding and offshore renewables value chains”, to contribute to the deliverables of WP3: D3.1 “Prioritization system2 and D3.2 “Baseline strategy identifying priorities, action lines and how the Pilot Experiences will contribute to the strategy”.
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4 Glossary

This glossary does not provide official definition but explanations based on recognized information sources

Term	Definition
Delphi	The Delphi method is based on the principle that forecasts from a structured group of individuals are more accurate than those from unstructured groups. Participating experts respond to questionnaires in two or more rounds. After each round, a facilitator provides an anonymized summary of the experts' forecasts from the previous round as well as the reasons on which their judgments were made.
Offshore Renewable Energy (ORE)	This term includes the offshore wind, wave and tidal energy, osmotic and OTEC (Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion). Generally used to designate Offshore Wind energy - MATES uses this term to refer also to Ocean Renewable energy, which includes four different energy segments: Tidal energy, Wave energy, Osmotic energy, OTEC (Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion).
Paradigm shifters	Key technologies that will have a more disruptive impact in the next years up to 2050 and for which the maritime industry is not prepared enough either in terms of technical capabilities or in terms of technological service and research offer
Shipbuilding	Building of ships and floating structures, including pleasure and sporting boats, repair and maintenance of ships and boats, and manufacture of marine equipment and marine machinery.
Paradigm shifter (ORE): Automation & advanced robotics	Automation refers to sophisticated automated systems, ideally with the additional capability for self-maintenance and repair, mostly requiring little or no human interaction to operate, apart from top-level guidance. Advanced robotics in maritime sectors refers to Unmanned systems (US), such as Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs), Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs), humanoid robots, etc. Control systems are key for the implementation of automation and advanced robotics in those sectors.
Paradigm shifter (ORE): Big data	Field that treats ways to analyse, systematically extract information from, or otherwise deal with data sets that are too large or complex to be dealt with by traditional data-processing application software. In offshore renewables the adoption of Big Data techniques is necessary due to the huge numbers of recorded data which are difficult to manage. Big Data is expected to mainly support managerial activities and real-time decision-making, for example, by optimizing logistics operations during the installation phase.
Paradigm shifter (ORE): 3D printing	Refers to a group of technologies where a three-dimensional object is created through the superimposition of layers of material. This technology allows an optimization of offshore construction logistics. It is already used in manufacturing and fabrication of offshore renewables components and moulds for testing procedures.
Paradigm shifter (ORE): Energy storage	Set of methods and technologies used to store various forms of energy. The implementation of energy storage can provide further benefits to the offshore renewables sector. It can ensure the development and improvement of grid integration, as well as the integration of offshore renewables in energy network infrastructures. In addition, it supports the sector's growth by facilitating the extensive installations of large-scale offshore facilities contributing to a reduction in their operational costs.
Paradigm shifter (ORE): Smart grid & smart sensors	A smart grid is an electricity network based on digital technology that is used to supply electricity to consumers via two-way digital communication. This system allows for monitoring, analysis, control and communication within the supply

	chain to help improve efficiency, reduce energy consumption and cost, and maximize the transparency and reliability of the energy supply chain. The smart grid was introduced with the aim of supporting the optimization of electricity generation, transmission and distribution by creating a highly interactive and responsive electricity grid that creates a balance between energy demand and supply. This technology is expected to increase stability, reliability and efficiency in offshore renewable energy operations.
Paradigm shifter (Shipbuilding): Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources	Alternative fuels are different substances which may be used as replacements for conventional fossil fuels that serve today as the main power source for propulsion and power generation in shipping. Alternatives include hydrogen, ammonia, biofuels, electricity, and fossil fuels such as CNG, LNG, LPG and GTL, only some of which have some decarbonisation potential.
Paradigm shifter (Shipbuilding): Digitalization	The use of digital technologies to change a business model in order to provide new revenue flows and value-producing opportunities; the process of moving to a digital business.
Paradigm shifter (Shipbuilding): Drones	Unmanned aerial vehicles that perform work and inspection in dangerous and confined spaces (i.e. turbines, cargo holds etc.) thus not only eliminating the risks in specific tasks but also capable of making extensive and efficient inspections.
Paradigm shifter (Shipbuilding): Green retrofitting	Any type of upgrade in an existing structure that is wholly or partly occupied in improving energy and environmental performance. The most important change in current regulations affecting global shipping is expected to address the maximum limit of sulphur contents in marine fuels which will drop from 3.50% to 0.5%.
Paradigm shifter (Shipbuilding): Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	This group of terms refers to the modernization of vessels based on the development and application of automated systems on ships. This kind of technology will be able to reduce the crew members needed to operate a ship, to increase the amount of cargo transported at a lower cost and to develop more sophisticated information systems based on sensors, cameras and radars.
Paradigm shifter (Shipbuilding): 3D printing	Group of technologies where a three-dimensional object is created through the superimposition of layers of material. It is expected to transform radically the industrial sector by reducing capital expenditures and the demand for human resources. This will enable time-saving procedures to be made in manufacturing processes, enable the use of more cost-efficient materials: it is anticipated that this technique will be exploited in the building of the infrastructures components.
Pilot Experiences	Planned actions to test the addressing of gaps in the skills of the workforces of the shipbuilding and offshore renewable energy industry
Higher education	Education provided by a university or a non-university institution, in accordance with the requirements and provisions of the <i>Education, Audio-visual and Culture Executive Agency</i> (https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/content/types-higher-education-institutions-79_en)

5 Executive summary

This report deals with the identification and analysis of emerging trends in the shipbuilding and offshore renewable energy sectors, with respect to new technologies, new skills, training programs and other associated parameters.

The key technologies considered are those for which the maritime industry is not enough prepared neither in terms of technical capabilities nor in terms of technological service and research offer.

The main aims and objectives are the clustering of the key technologies in 3-time horizons and the description of future scenarios on skills and competences, as well as gaps in the current and foreseen levels sectors at the short, mid and long-term.

The methodology adopted herein is comprised of a critical review, mobilization of experts and a Delphi exercise. The Delphi exercise was the last consequent step-tool to collect and analyse the opinions of experts in order to achieve the objectives of this task. The trends and driving forces dealt with and identified during the Delphi survey are foreseen to affect the employability of the Shipbuilding and Offshore Renewable Energy sectors, making it necessary for all professionals to adapt to the new developments by following dynamic and lifelong approaches with shorter turnarounds.

The main points-findings of this report are as follows:

1. All of the paradigm shifters considered herein would become mainstream by the year 2030, and many of them are already mainstream in particular sub-sectors of the SB and ORE industries.
2. All genders of the workforce would be equally affected in all time horizons considered
3. The ages that would become more affected in the short term (i.e. from 2019 to 2025) are those from 35 years old and above, in the mid-term (i.e. from year 2025 to 2030) the ages from 35 to 55 years old and in the long term (i.e. from year 2030 and beyond) the ages from 55 and above. In all time horizons, the workforce below the age of 25 years old would remain unaffected.
4. None of the affected occupations would disappear, but the workforce in the vast majority of the affected occupations would require retraining in order to remain employable.
5. The most important skills and competences for the workforce to have would be: a) Engineering Skills and b) Transferable Skills.
6. Vocational Training (VET) either by the current employer or/and by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE institutes etc.) would play a key role to provide the required skills and competences to the affected workforce in certain time horizons.
7. The most effective educational methods that obtained the majority of opinions were the: a) lifelong learning, b) webinars combined with training on the job.
8. It is expected that around half of the emerging occupations (out of 14 in the SB sector and 22 in the ORE sector) will be new occupations and the other half will be existing occupations that would gain relevance by the advancement of paradigm shifters considered.

The conclusions and comments are presented in more detail in Chapter 9.

6 Aims and Objectives

The main aims and objectives of this task are to cluster paradigm shifters in 3-time horizons: i) the short-term, ii) the mid-term and iii) the long-term and to describe future scenarios on skills and competences, as well as gaps in the current and foreseen levels sector in the short, mid and long-term.

According to the initial work plan of task 2.3, the three time horizons are as follows:

- i. short-term : by the year 2020
- ii. mid-term: by the year 2030
- iii. long-term: by the year 2050

These time horizons appear to be short for the purposes of the subject task. Some pertinent reasons are the following:

- a) *short-term* ends before the end of the MATES project
- b) the policy making organizations/authorities (i.e., education, public administrations etc.) would need a longer-term foresight

Therefore, following a debate among the members of the MATES consortium, it was agreed to use the following revised time horizons in the subsequent work:

- i. short-term : by the year 2025
- ii. mid-term: from year 2025 to year 2030
- iii. long-term: beyond year 2030

7 Methodology

7.1 Critical review

A critical review and analysis of the existing needs for education, training and skills in the sectors of shipbuilding and offshore renewables in Europe was conducted to address current shortages and gaps in relevant skills and qualifications. The critical review was based on an extended literature review of 392 documents and 153 projects already available in the MATES repository of relevant information. This was complemented by the mobilization of experts and stakeholders from the Shipbuilding and Offshore renewable energy sectors during two (2) rounds of workshops conducted at five (5) European countries [REF. D1.2 State of the Art report; D1.3 Regional Workshops¹].

7.2 Paradigm shifters

The afore-mentioned actions identified the following paradigm shifters as the most significant for the future as well as other input parameters (i.e., lists of existing occupations and training methods etc.) which formed the basis for the Delphi exercise:

A. Offshore Renewable Energies

1. Automation & Advanced robotics
2. 3D Printing
3. Smart grid & Smart sensors
4. Big data
5. Energy storage

¹ Reports of the workshops are available on the MATES website, section Deliverables 1.3, Mobilisation Workshops and 2.1 and 2.2 Baseline validation workshops and final validation workshop <https://www.projectmates.eu/results/deliverables/>

B. Shipbuilding

1. Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics
2. Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources
3. Digitalization
4. 3D Printing
5. Green retrofitting
6. Drones

7.3 Collect and analyse the opinions of experts (Delphi consultation)

The Delphi methodology was utilized in this task as a method of aggregating experts' opinions through a series of iterative questionnaires with a goal of achieving a group consensus and is based on the assumption that judgments of a structured group are more valid than judgments of individuals. It contains key characteristics which help participants to focus on the issues at hand and separate Delphi from other methodologies:

- Anonymity of the participants: This prevents the authority, personality, or reputation of some participants from dominating others in the process.
- Iteration that allows participants to revise their perspectives.
- Regular Feedback: Allows participants to comment on the responses of others, the progress of the panel as a whole, and to revise their own forecasts and opinions in real time.

The information retrieved from the shortlisted key paradigm shifters identified as most significant for the future include the following:

- The effect on current and future jobs
- Requirements of emerging jobs
- Timeframe of changes
- Critical technologies required for the evolution of the paradigms

Quantitative (i.e. numbered ratings, % etc.) as well as qualitative (i.e. discussion of the closed form and free text answers with members of the thematic groups and members of the MATES consortium) assessment was utilized in the analysis of the collected data to determine the degree of convergence of experts' opinions. So, high convergence rates express a high consensus in the opinions of the Delphi participants. It is important to note that room of alternative views on issues remained, which showed low convergence rates. This is acceptable for such a broad topic like the future trends and scenarios that involve new technologies, skills, training, education and socioeconomic factors.

In order to optimize the use of time and resources for completing the subject Delphi exercise, it was decided to use a detailed 1st round and, based on the results, to proceed with the least possible number of rounds for achieving consensus. The Delphi questionnaires were split into two different parts of which the first one dealt with: a) The Shipbuilding sector and b) The Offshore renewable energy sector. The incorporated questions were of closed form as well as of free-text. The following types of questions were used as appropriate:

- Multi-select question: A question that allows the respondent to select more than one item/answer per row/column
- Single-select question: A question that allows the respondent to select only one item/answer per row/column
- Rating scale question: A question that allows the respondent to select a number from 1 to 10 as a response (1: Not at all likely, 10: Extremely likely)

7.3.1 Profile of the participants

Delphi questionnaires were developed and distributed to two specific groups of MATES registered experts (<http://whowhomates.com/>) in the sectors of i) Shipbuilding and ii) Offshore Renewable Energy. In order to obtain high quality data, these groups were balanced with respect to key characteristics: organization type (i.e. academic, Industry etc.), experience level, genders, age, geographical area (sea basin) etc.

The following figures show the breakdown of characteristics of the participants.

Figure 1 Age of the experts who participated in the Delphi survey

Figure 2 Experience level (years of experience) of the experts who participated in the Delphi survey

Figure 3 Sectors of expertise of the Delphi survey participants

Figure 4 Proportion* of women and men participating in the Delphi Survey (*data based on the number of participants who declared their gender)

Figure 5 Size of organizations participated in the Delphi survey

Figure 6 Sea basin of organizations participating in the Delphi survey

Figure 7 Type of Organizations participating in the Delphi survey

Response	Total	% of responses	%
Spain	27	<div style="width: 33%;"></div>	33%
United Kingdom	12	<div style="width: 14%;"></div>	14%
Greece	11	<div style="width: 13%;"></div>	13%
Portugal	8	<div style="width: 10%;"></div>	10%
Germany	4	<div style="width: 5%;"></div>	5%
Belgium	4	<div style="width: 5%;"></div>	5%
Bulgaria	3	<div style="width: 4%;"></div>	4%
Other, please specify	3	<div style="width: 4%;"></div>	4%
France	2	<div style="width: 2%;"></div>	2%
Poland	2	<div style="width: 2%;"></div>	2%
Netherlands	2	<div style="width: 2%;"></div>	2%
Italy	2	<div style="width: 2%;"></div>	2%
Denmark	1	<div style="width: 1%;"></div>	1%
Cyprus	1	<div style="width: 1%;"></div>	1%
Ireland	1	<div style="width: 1%;"></div>	1%

Total respondents: 83
Skipped question: 0

*The European shipbuilding sector is actively involved in maintaining, repairing and retrofitting vessels, and with regard to the construction part, it is mainly active in the production of cruise vessels and specialized vessels [REF. Sdoukopoulos, E. et al. (2020)]. The countries shown in the Figure above have shipbuilding activities which follow that pattern. The above Figure refers to: Top countries w.r.t capacity of offshore wind turbines in Europe: 1-United Kingdom, 2-Germany, 3-Denmark, 4-Belgium, 5-Netherlands [Source: WindEurope, 2019]; Top countries w.r.t capacity in ocean energy: 1-France, 2-UK, 3-Spain [Source: IRENA, 2019]

7.3.2 First round of Delphi consultation

The 1st round of the Delphi focused onto clarifying the importance and potential time of adoption of the paradigm shifters presented (see 1st Delphi Questionnaire in Annex A). The questionnaire was distributed to 176 experts (the recorded final participation was 47%), who were asked to answer 147 (main) questions in total. The first round was open for 15 days (from 11-03-2019 until 25-03-2019). After the data collection phase, the data were analysed in order to re-formulate statements and generate the 2nd round questionnaire. High convergence rates were observed in the majority of the answers, which expressed a high consensus in the opinions of the experts.

In the 1st Delphi round only, a special set of three (3) questions was addressed to the experts from Enterprises, Industry Associations and Clusters to give their opinions on the following items:

- a. Whether it is easy/difficult to find employees with the required skills
- b. If the currently available educational and training programs in their country can provide the required skills to the workforce
- c. Which they think are current skills' gaps in their sectors

7.3.3 Second round of Delphi consultation

The 2nd round focused on the educational methods, emerging and affected occupations (see 2nd Delphi Questionnaire in Annex A).

The opinions of the respondents from the 1st round supported that all of the paradigm shifters dealt with so far, for each sector, would become mainstream by the year 2030. So, the same paradigm shifters were considered in the 2nd round. Also, there were many interesting results from the 1st Delphi round, which were provided to the participants of the 2nd round as graphs and many of the 2nd round questions referred to those results, asking the respondents for their opinion on how to further explore the needs and trends for skills, training etc.

Only the experts who responded in the 1st Delphi round were invited to participate in the second round in order to maintain consistency of the results. So, the 2nd questionnaire was distributed to 83 experts (the recorded final participation was 77%), who were asked to answer 49 questions in total. The 2nd round remained open for 10 days (from 02-05-2019 until 13-05-2019). High convergence rates were observed in the majority of the answers, which expressed a high consensus in the views of the experts.

8 Results

8.1 Future trends and new technologies

8.1.1 Shipbuilding sector

8.1.1.1 Shipping environmental legislation

Over the past years, a number of changes in shipping regulations have been introduced, mainly by the International Maritime Organization (IMO), which have induced significant changes to the design and operation of commercial vessels. The main driving force behind those changes was the prevention of pollution on the marine environment and the overall protection of life and property.

Such a significant change was the amendment of the MARPOL 73/78 convention in 1992, which made double hulls mandatory for all new tankers of 5,000 DWT and above, following the severe environmental impact of the Exxon Valdez accident and the introduction of the Oil Pollution Act of 1990 (OPA 90) in the United States of America. This came in addition to the 1974 amendment of the SOLAS convention and the introduction of double bottoms in passenger and cargo ships. Those legislative revisions imposed significant changes in traditional vessel designs used at that time. They required the establishment of new construction procedures as well as the adoption of a different operational approach and a redefinition of maintenance and repairing activities throughout the life cycle of a vessel. The post-production phase of the value chain was also affected, since the current, to that time, single bottom / hull vessels failing to meet the relevant requirements had to be retrofitted or taken out of service and dismantled within a specific period of time.

Today, the key trends in the shipbuilding sector focus mainly on (a) lowering operating costs and (b) the 'greening' of relevant operations by reducing the vessels' air, noise and water emissions thus enhancing their overall energy efficiency. Following relevant amendments to MARPOL Annex VI, the global sulphur cap has been gradually reduced over the past years, with a bigger change expected to enter into force as of January 1st, 2020 when it will drop from the current 3.5% to 0.5% in addition to Sulphur Emission Control Areas (SECAs) where stricter limits exist (i.e. Baltic Sea, North Sea, US Caribbean Sea and North American Sea area). New areas to be designated as SECAs are also currently under investigation (e.g. Mediterranean Sea).

With regard to energy efficiency, the Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) for new vessels and the Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP) for existing vessels entered into force in 2013 promoting the use of more energy efficient equipment and engines. These are to be further strengthened following the adoption of the 'Initial IMO strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from ships' which sets a clear vision for the reduction, and the eventual phasing out, of greenhouse gas emissions from international shipping. Furthermore, environmental shipping index schemes (e.g. Clean Shipping Index, Green Awards, etc.) are gaining increased attention and many shipping lines are certifying their vessels to them so that they can exploit the benefits that many port authorities provide (e.g. reduced dues) as well as benefit from the further enhancement of their corporate image since many customers / shippers highly value environmentally friendly operations leading to 'green' supply chains.

In order to successfully meet the requirements of the afore-mentioned legislations, naval architects, marine engineers as well as a number of other relevant occupations have abandoned designs and technologies that once served as the norm and have developed innovative concepts and introduced new technological solutions for enhancing the environmental and energy performance of vessels. These include advanced ship designs, dual-fuel engines or engines only using alternative fuels (e.g. LNG), installation of open- or close-loop scrubber systems, antifouling paints, etc. Obviously

technological advancements are rapidly penetrating the industry and the proper use of ever increasing data is essential for maximizing potential benefits including environmental ones, besides many others. Given its specialization and considerable investments in advanced technologies compared to global competitors, the European shipbuilding industry could lead such developments, which in turn could contribute towards increasing its global market share in the near future when the new shipping environmental regulations will enter into force.

8.1.1.2 *Alternative Fuels*

Alternative fuels are different substances which may be used as a replacement of conventional fossil fuels that serve today as the main power source for propulsion and power generation in shipping. Those mainly include Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG), Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG), biodiesel, bio-alcohol, hydrogen, ammonia as well as electricity (i.e. batteries and fuel cells) and fuels produced from biomass (DNV-GL, 2018).

Today the number of new-build vessels or vessels that have been converted for using alternative fuels is growing fast. LNG serves as the main option and accounts for the widest applicability while electrification is also gaining momentum and interest with several relevant projects being ongoing and at different stages of development.

As mentioned above, the number of LNG-powered vessels is increasing at a fast pace every year following mainly the introduction of new environmental regulations in shipping as well as investments on building the necessary bunkering infrastructure along major trade routes so that demand can be facilitated. More specifically, by the end of 2017, approximately 118 LNG-powered vessels were in service worldwide, while another 97 were on order, which represents an increase of 23% compared to the previous year (LNG World Shipping, 2017).

Besides LNG, there is also a considerable number of vessels that are using other forms of energy with their deployment however being quite limited at the moment. More specifically, in 2015, the first electric power passenger vessel entered into service in Norway capable of transporting, through the use of 3 lithium-ion batteries, approximately 120 cars and 360 passengers. The electrification of vessels has actually attracted increased attention over the past few years, with the relevant technology presenting significant advantages but also considerable disadvantages that should be carefully taken into account. Obviously, the elimination of air emissions accounts is the main advantage while important reductions in operating costs as well as in maintenance and service costs stemming from the lower complexity of electric motors compared to combustion engines leading to a longer life-time of the relevant equipment, could be also driving investments in electric vessels, supporting in that way their wider deployment in the near future. However, those initial investment costs remain high at the moment while new charging infrastructure is also required so that electric vessels can be deployed in a wider network going beyond short-distance routes that currently only serve due to limited battery capacity and long charging time that is required.

In several cases, vessels are equipped with dual-fuel engines that can use both methanol and fuel oil or marine gas oil (MGO), while biodiesel fuels (e.g. hydrogenated vegetable oil - HVO) prove also to be used in certain sea areas and countries (e.g. Norway) within Europe (DNV-GL, 2018).

The wider exploitation of alternative fuels in shipping in the near future will further amplify the implications that have already emerged for the shipbuilding and ship-repair industry. New vessel designs serving for example energy storage requirements for electric vessels as well as new engine designs exploiting different energy sources thus contributing towards reduced fuel consumption as well as other new relevant concepts, are expected to be further integrated into the line of work of relevant occupational profiles, indicating in that way the need for properly updating or modernizing current skills and competences so that the expected efficiencies can be fully realized.

8.1.1.3 Autonomous Vessels

One of the key areas the maritime transport industry has been lately placing increased attention on and with significant R&D investments already undertaken, is the development and deployment of autonomous vessels reducing the number of required crew members and ultimately moving towards fully unmanned vessels. Automation of transport systems proves to be more advanced in road transport but is now gradually moving into other modes as well, exploiting the distinct characteristics the latter present. Ongoing research is expected to considerably enhance the situational awareness of vessels through the development of more sophisticated sensors, the better utilization of electronic chart display and information systems (ECDIS), cameras, radars etc.

The relevant opportunities that have emerged for the European shipbuilding industry are substantial and should be fully exploited. To this end, new sets of advanced digital skills and skills in mechatronics are required with regard to several occupations involved in different segments of the whole value chain. Unmanned shipping is considered by many as a technological innovation that will contribute towards further lowering costs for moving freight overseas. Since no crew will be required, the vessels' superstructure (i.e. bridge and accommodation facilities) becomes unnecessary. To this end, loading capacity can be increased while operating and maintenance / repair costs can be significantly reduced.

Despite intensive research efforts, significant time is still required for developing fully unmanned vessels especially with regard to their deployment in major international trade routes since the associated risks are greater. Furthermore, another important barrier is the absence of the appropriate legal framework governing the use and operation of these vessels. Approximately 14 IMO conventions will need to be amended in order to support the deployment of fully unmanned vessels. More specifically new or updated regulations will be required for navigation, collision prevention, cargo supervision, etc.

8.1.2 Offshore renewable energy sector

In line with the results of an extended literature review, the offshore renewable energy sector will be characterized, in the next few decades, by significant technological advancements that will impose a substantial impact on its value chain. Digitalization is being regarded as the main technological trend of the future which can contribute towards the further growth of the sector, attracting an increased investment interest and the participation of several industry actors, facilitating in that way the implementation of a large number of offshore renewable energy projects that in turn will heavily increase employability levels in the respective countries. A wide and diverse set of different technologies is currently under consideration presenting different levels of market maturity and deployment. Those include automation, robotics, data science analytics, Artificial Intelligence (AI), 3D printing etc., and their uptake is expected to revolutionize the offshore renewable energy industry by reducing capital and operational costs and increasing productivity levels. To this end, a wider industrialization of the sector is expected, across its whole value chain and especially in the manufacturing, operation and maintenance components while supporting services (e.g. vessel operations and logistics) will be also affected to a considerable extent. This will create in turn new jobs to be filled by young employees equipped, through targeted educational and training programs, with the necessary digital skills (ETIPWind, 2018).

The key technologies to be introduced / integrated in the offshore renewable energy sector are described below with estimations, where available, of their expected impact on the sector and its value chain.

8.1.2.1 *New technical specifications (e.g. bigger turbines, floating platforms, etc.)*

A major trend in reference to offshore wind energy, is the building of bigger turbines and the installation of the relevant infrastructure in deeper waters (>50m depth) as a means to reduce costs and improve efficiency. In the near future, the size of turbines is expected to increase (i.e. the rotor diameter), and so is their energy capacity which is expected to reach approximately 12MW (Deign, 2018; IEA, 2018). Furthermore, new concepts are currently being investigated for installing offshore wind farms into deeper waters where winds are stronger and more stable. These concepts mainly refer to floating platforms, hub islands and hybrid systems.

The development of floating wind platforms is quite attractive as a concept, since those structures prove to be easier to install and maintain (Burger, 2016). As floating wind concepts have already been implemented in a number of projects (e.g. Hywind in Scotland and Norway, WindFloat in Portugal, Floatgen in France, etc.) with some of them even becoming operational, floating offshore wind energy is expected to become, within the next decade, a common and widespread practice (GWEC, 2017). The most suitable locations for such structures are considered to be the European side of the Atlantic Ocean as well as the Mediterranean Sea, where floating wind projects have already approved for France (IRENA, 2016; OffshoreWIND.biz, 2016).

Hub islands are large-scale infrastructures that consist of interlinked offshore wind turbines or solar panels and one or more artificial islands (Rhodri et al., 2015; GreenMatch, 2018; Groot, 2018). The latter facilitate the placement of converters, can serve as large scale energy storage and thus can act as the home base of engineers working on relevant projects. Hub islands can significantly reduce associated costs and cable losses attributed to the long distance between offshore structures and the shoreline (Groot, 2018).

Hybrid systems can also serve as another option. More specifically, offshore wind infrastructures may be combined with wave energy devices or even solar panels in order to improve energy generation efficiency, since more than one renewable energy source can be exploited, and thus both operational and capital costs can be reduced (Failla et al., 2015; Nilsson et al., 2015; Pérez-Collazo et al., 2015; Ocean Energy Systems, 2018).

The main aim driving the development of these concepts is the generation of a more stable electric power which will enhance the reliability in offshore renewables, and thus will boost in that way further growth in the sector. The whole value chain is expected to be affected, as well as supporting services. The impact on manufacturing processes is expected to be considerable, as the different components of offshore renewable energy projects are to become quite larger, as mentioned above, which will also demand bigger facilities able to handle the required production. Installation, construction, operation, maintenance and de/re-commissioning activities are also expected to be affected due to more difficult access to the relevant infrastructure. As a result, new requirements will be made with regard to plants' teleoperations, human resources, equipment and installation components transportation, logistics and vessel operations.

8.1.2.2 *New materials*

New requirements are expected to emerge also in the offshore renewable energy sector with regard to materials. Most of these relate to offshore wind energy, since this technology is the more mature one but the sector also faces important challenges due to the exposure of the relevant infrastructure to frequent extreme conditions. Research on new materials is currently on-going for the offshore oil and gas sector but given the similarities those structures present, in terms of pressures experienced, the results can be also exploited by all offshore renewable energy sub-sectors supporting the realization of synergies among them (Tong, 2019). The main goal of the relevant research initiatives is to develop advanced lightweight, fatigue- and corrosion-resistant, environmentally friendly, recyclable, durable and cost-efficient materials. The latter can contribute towards optimizing the

performance of the offshore renewable energy system, reduce costs, and extend service life and decommissioning (Setvati et al., 2014; Dvorak, 2017; Powers, 2017; Bossler, 2018; Masi et al., 2018).

Various prototypes have been developed including composite materials, fiber-glass, carbon fiber, bio-composites, epoxy matrix composites, thermoplastic foam, natural composites, hybrid, and nano-engineered composites (Setvati et al., 2014; plastemart.com, 2016; Mishnaevsky et al., 2017; Acumen Research and Consulting, 2018; Dvorak, 2018). Their application ranges from installation to repair or even fire protection, while they can also be used in different offshore components such as grids, cable support systems and sub-sea structural components (Setvati et al., 2014). New uses have also emerged in the offshore wind energy sector, related to the production of turbine blades, mooring systems, nacelles, towers, bases and even floating platforms (Swolfs, 2017; Acumen Research and Consulting, 2018; Bossler, 2018; Dvorak, 2018; Head et al., 2016).

The development of new materials will transform the technical specifications of offshore infrastructures, increasing the demand for expertise in materials engineering. Furthermore, the lifecycle of infrastructures can be extended, adding in that way further value to offshore renewables through a longer period of operation.

8.1.2.3 Energy storage

One of the biggest challenges in renewable energy production and consumption is the efficient management of energy supply and demand. In some cases, energy generation exceeds energy needs leading to loss of the energy surplus, while in other cases, the produced amount of energy is far less than demanded and as a result energy needs cannot be supported efficiently. These insufficiencies constrain the growth of the renewable energies sector, especially of large-scale offshore renewables. Energy storage is considered to be the most suitable solution for balancing energy demand and supply by storing energy surplus in order to use it when it is needed.

In addition, the implementation of energy storage can provide further benefits to the offshore renewables sector. It can ensure the development and improvement of grid integration, as well as the integration of offshore renewables in energy network infrastructures (Mortelmans, 2018). Furthermore, it supports the sector's growth by facilitating the wide installation of large-scale offshore facilities as it contributes to the reduction of their operational costs. Last but not least, energy storage is a useful expedient for the realization of energy transition from conventional to renewable energy technologies (Spro et al., 2015; Scott, 2018; ETIPWind, 2018).

Research on energy storage applications is now focused on developing cost-effective, energy efficient and environmentally friendly solutions, as the existing storage devices consist of chemicals that pollute the marine environment, and materials of high cost (Graham, 2018). Widespread applications are the pumped storage systems (PSS) and compressed air energy storage systems, but further research is required (Katsaprakakis, 2016).

Energy storage can provide stability and reliability to energy production, and balance between energy demand and supply. Due to these potentials, it is expected that operational activities will be improved and their lifespan extended, while maintenance will be more intensive. As far as construction and installation processes are concerned, they could be affected, as energy storage devices should be taken into consideration in the projects' implementation. Last but not least, energy storage capacity could boost the enlargement of the offshore renewables sector.

8.1.2.4 Remote Sensing, Automation and Advanced Robotics

Automation, Advanced Robotics, Remote Sensing, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) are 'gradually being adopted in offshore renewables via the exploitation of Unmanned Systems (US), such as Autonomous Vessels, Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs), Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) and Drones. The afore-mentioned technological advances are intended to be used in various activities of the

offshore renewables value chain, mainly aiming to improve access, construction, installation, teleoperation, inspection, monitoring, maintenance and performance upgrade (Chen et al., 2014; O'Donnell et al., 2015; Grey, 2017; Chartron et al., 2018; Morales et al., 2018). For instance, AUVs are recommended for marine surveys, ROUVs (Remotely Operated Underwater Vehicles) for sub-sea cable installations, drones for inspections of turbines and infrastructures, human robotics for maintenance and repair processes and sensors for automated or teleoperation and monitoring of the turbines (Elvander et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2014; Grey, 2017; Ørsted, 2018).

As far as remote sensing is concerned, sensors and LiDAR are the key technologies implemented in offshore renewables for infrastructures' health and behaviour forecasting, detection, monitoring and diagnosis, such as sub-sea cables health monitoring or wind turbines problems detection and diagnosis (Azcona et al., 2017; Flynn et al., 2018). In addition to these, they are exploited for weather monitoring and prediction, which contributes to the operation of the turbines management (Hasager et al., 2008; Chartron et al., 2018). Their usefulness lies in the avoidance of unnecessary inspections, the improvement of the operations, the prediction and maximization of the infrastructure's life cycle.

Apart from that, these advancements have the potential to improve safety and security in marine environment, which is characterized by hazardous, extreme weather conditions that puts human lives at risk (Grey, 2017). Their usage is also expected to reduce costs and optimize efficiency and safety in operations, since operation management and workability are improved and fewer human resources will be needed (Chartron et al., 2018). To this end, US could affect value chain by reducing its length, since valuable time-savings can be achieved due to the avoidance of weather conditions barriers and human resources and equipment transfer.

Taking into account the afore-mentioned benefits, the whole value chain of offshore renewables is expected to be influenced. Project planning could be supported by automated surveys and mappings, while construction, installation, operation, maintenance and de-/recommissioning would be significantly influenced by shortening their length, reducing their costs and facilitating their processes, especially concerning vessel operations and logistics. However, fewer human resources would be needed due to the use of robots and automated systems. This would create new job positions, inducing a need for re-training in order to provide the required digital skills to the affected workforce.

8.1.2.5 Smart grid, smart devices, smart sensors, Internet of Things, Cloud computing

Integration of offshore renewable energies to grid network is a challenging procedure that facilitates energy transition from conventional to renewable energy sources (Foster, 2012). Smart grid, as well as smart devices and sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) and Cloud computing, are key technologies for the realization of the afore-mentioned (Camacho et al., 2011; Chartron et al., 2018; Richard, 2018). Grid integration supports the optimization of electricity generation, transmission and distribution by creating a highly interactive and responsive electricity grid (Muttaqi et al., 2019). In this way, balance between energy demand and supply can be achieved in the most cost-efficient manner (British Consulate, n.d.).

Smart grid is expected to revolutionize energy production, delivery and consumption by ensuring stability, reliability and efficiency in offshore renewable energies operations (Camacho et al., 2011; Muttaqi et al., 2019). As a result, operation and maintenance procedures of the value chain can be enabled, while the sector can be boosted and enlarged.

8.1.2.6 Data analytics & Big Data

The devices used in offshore renewables are already equipped with technologies responsible for collecting data with reference to their performance, such as sensors and IoT. The data collection is now established to include real-time records about weather, wind speeds and the performance of the turbines, leading to a huge number of records that are difficult to manage. This requires the adoption

of Big Data techniques and methods that can be useful throughout the whole offshore renewables value chain and significantly reduce the length of data processing and analytics. Big Data is expected to support mainly managerial activities and real-time decision-making, for example, by optimizing logistics operations during the installation phase. It is also mentioned, that it can improve operation and maintenance predictability by providing precise forecasting and analysis in order to increase power production and reduce operational costs (Bagnall et al., n.d.; Helsen et al., 2016; Henry, 2017; Chartron et al., 2018; Gerdes, 2018a).

According to Chartron et al. (2018), Big Data methods can be implemented in combination with other state-of-the-art data science technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence for supporting risk assessments, and consist of various techniques applicable in offshore renewables (Henry, 2017; Imaz, 2017).

8.1.2.7 Block chain

Digitalization in offshore renewables and especially the usage of Internet of Things, smart grid and smart devices emerge as issues in accordance with the efficient communication and data exchange between devices, as well as data security. According to Andoni et al. (2019), Blockchain technology could cover the afore-mentioned challenges, as it can support automation, asset management and grid management in the wider energy sector by improving the control of decentralized energy systems and microgrids (Baraniuk, 2017; Baranko, 2018). As a result, it could have several uses across the offshore renewables value chain from management procedures to billing, energy trading and marketing among others. According to estimations, Blockchain and its applications are expected to revolutionize the energy sector and offshore renewables in particular (Keivanpour et al., 2019; Schwarz, 2018).

8.1.2.8 3D printing

3D printing is expected to transform radically the industrial sector, by reducing capital expenditures and demand in human resources and saving time in manufacturing processes. Other benefits are estimated to be the ability to use more cost-efficient materials and the optimization of offshore construction logistics. (Lam & Ma, 2016; Landmart.com, 2016; Chartron et al., 2018, Gerdes, 2018b; IEEFA, 2018)

It is already used in manufacturing and the fabrication of offshore renewables components and moulds for testing procedures and it is intended to be applied for commercial offshore renewables products, too (WALiD project). Apart from that, concrete additive manufacturing is also planned to be exploited in the building of the infrastructures components, such as foundations, turbine towers, etc. (IEEFA, 2018).

The benefits from 3D printing affect mainly manufacturing procedures, supporting massive production and enabling cost savings and time savings. The usefulness of additive manufacturing can also be expanded to maintenance activities reducing the duration of spare parts manufacturing. This innovation may reduce the need for human resources, but, taking into consideration that it can increase production rates and the demand for components, these human resources can be absorbed by other similar projects.

8.2 Shipbuilding

8.2.1 Results of the 1st Delphi Round

8.2.1.1 1st Delphi Round, Questions No.1 and No.3 (out of 12)

“WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?” (Rating scale question) and “IN WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?” (Single-select question)

In relation to the questions “Will this paradigm shifter become mainstream?” and “In which time horizon this paradigm shifter is likely to become mainstream?” the majority of the Delphi participants agreed that all of the paradigm shifters considered are expected to become mainstream by the year 2030 at the latest. The list of PSs below is in the order of their likelihood of becoming mainstream.

1. Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics (yes: 87%)
2. Digitalization (yes: 87%)
3. Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources (yes: 83%)
4. Drones (yes: 73%)
5. Green retrofitting (yes: 70%)
6. 3D Printing (yes: 59%)

8.2.1.2 1st Delphi Round, Question No.2 (out of 12)

“WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?” (Rating scale question)

In relation to the question “Will this paradigm shifter affect (adversely or favourably) the current job situation in Europe?” the majority of the Delphi participants agreed that all PSs considered would have an effect as shown in the following list (in the order of their likelihood to affect the current job situation).

1. Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics (yes: 79%)
2. Digitalization (yes: 75%)
3. Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources (yes: 67%)
4. Drones (yes: 55%)
5. 3D Printing (yes: 52%)
6. Green retrofitting (yes: 50%)

8.2.1.3 1st Delphi Round, Question No.4 (out of 12)

“HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?” (Single-select question)

In relation to the question “How would the current job situation be affected (adversely or favourably) by the advancement of the subject paradigm shifter?” the Delphi participants agreed that all Shipbuilding Paradigm Shifters would Slightly Affected-Affect the current job situation in Europe by the year 2025. It was also found that the following PSs would have a strong effect on the current job situation from year 2025 to 2030 (reshape/fully reshape) and continue similarly from year 2030 and beyond:

- Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics
- Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources
- Digitalization

The opinions of the same respondents showed that the *Drones* and *Green retrofitting* PSs would have a noticeable effect (slightly affected-Affected) from the present time and up to the year 2030. This effect would be considerably reduced from year 2030 and beyond.

Table 1 Effect of the Paradigm Shifters on the current job situation in Europe (Shipbuilding)

Paradigm shifters	How would the current job situation be affected (Shipbuilding)				
	Slightly Affected	Affected	Reshaped	Fully reshaped	
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	By the year 2025	38%	38%	19%	
	From year 2025 to 2030		42%	40%	17%
	From year 2030 and beyond		9%	40%	45%
Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources	By the year 2025	47%	40%	9%	2%
	From year 2025 to 2030	18%	38%	33%	7%
	From year 2030 and beyond	13%	18%	29%	31%
Digitalization	By the year 2025	28%	49%	14%	7%
	From year 2025 to 2030	7%	35%	40%	16%
	From year 2030 and beyond	2%	12%	40%	42%
3D printing	By the year 2025	49%	33%	5%	3%
	From year 2025 to 2030	21%	49%	21%	3%
	From year 2030 and beyond	8%	41%	31%	15%
Green retrofitting	By the year 2025	40%	35%	10%	5%
	From year 2025 to 2030	20%	30%	23%	10%
	From year 2030 and beyond	15%	30%	8%	23%
Drones	By the year 2025	43%	33%	5%	10%
	From year 2025 to 2030	29%	33%	19%	10%
	From year 2030 and beyond	24%	38%	10%	14%

8.2.1.4 1st Delphi Round, Question No.5 (out of 12)

“WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS² WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED?” (Multi-select question)

In relation to the question “What existing occupations will be most affected (adversely or favourably) and by when?” the Delphi participants agreed that the most affected occupations per PS are as shown in the following Table.

Table 2. Most affected occupations against predicted Paradigm Shifters (Shipbuilding)

Paradigm shifters	Most affected occupations (Shipbuilding)
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Naval architect - Electromechanical engineer - Electromechanical equipment assembler - Marine engineer
Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marine engineering technician - Marine engineering drafter - Marine engineer - Naval architect
Digitalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marine engineering drafter - Electromechanical drafter - Electromechanical engineering technician - Marine engineer
3D printing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electromechanical engineering technician - Vessel engine assembler - Electromechanical equipment assembler - Computer numerical control (CNC) machine operator - Welder
Green retrofitting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marine engineer - Naval architect - Marine engineering technician
Drones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vessel assembly supervisor - Vessel assembly inspector - Marine surveyor

8.2.1.5 1st Delphi Round, Question No.6 (out of 12)

“WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?” (Multi-select question)

In relation to the question “What transferable skills should the adversely affected workforce have in order to be employable in a different job type/sector etc.?” the majority of responses support that the adversely affected workforce will need to have all of the transferable skills shown in the Table below by the year 2025.

² Occupations are according to the ESCO classification, based on the identification made in [Sdoukopoulos, E. et al. (2020)]

Table 3 Transferable skills that the adversely affected workforce should have (Shipbuilding)

Paradigm shifters	Transferable skills that the adversely affected workforce should have (Shipbuilding)
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critical thinking and problem-solving - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Communication and collaboration
Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexibility and adaptability - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Critical thinking and problem-solving
Digitalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Creative thinking and innovation - Critical thinking and problem-solving
3D printing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Flexibility and adaptability - Communication and collaboration
Green retrofitting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexibility and adaptability - Knowledge management and transfer - Critical thinking and problem-solving
Drones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexibility and adaptability - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Critical thinking and problem-solving

The two most important skills for the workforce to have, that are consistent in all paradigm shifters, are:

- Critical thinking and problem-solving
- Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy

8.2.1.6 1st Delphi Round, Question No.7 (out of 12)

“WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?” (Single-select question)

In relation to the question “What ages of the workforce would be most (adversely) affected and when?” the majority of responses support that:

- The ages above 55 years old would be the most adversely affected ages from year 2030 and beyond
- The ages up to 25 years old would be the least adversely affected in all time horizons
- All ages above 35 years old would be almost equally affected between years 2025-2030

Table 4 Ages of the workforce affected by the advancement of Paradigm Shifters (Shipbuilding)

Ages of workforce affected	Paradigm Shifters (Shipbuilding)					
	Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources	Digitalization	3D printing	Green retrofitting	Drones
<2025 (% respondents)						
Up to 25 years old	4%	2%	2%	5%	0	0
25-35	13%	14%	17%	3%	5%	25%
35-45	11%	28%	26%	29%	35%	15%
45-55	38%	23%	26%	34%	30%	20%
>55 years old	34%	33%	29%	29%	30%	40%
2025-2030 (% respondents)						
Up to 25 years old	2%	0%	5%	3%	0	5%
25-35	11%	14%	14%	5%	24%	25%
35-45	30%	33%	26%	37%	32%	20%
45-55	34%	30%	31%	29%	16%	25%
>55 years old	23%	23%	24%	26%	27%	25%
>2030 (% respondents)						
Up to 25 years old	9%	14%	14%	5%	5%	10%
25-35	21%	12%	12%	29%	24%	25%
35-45	23%	26%	24%	8%	22%	15%
45-55	21%	23%	17%	18%	14%	25%
>55 years old	26%	26%	33%	39%	35%	25%

8.2.1.7 1st Delphi Round, Question No.8 (out of 12)

“DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?” (Single-select question)

In relation to the question “Do you consider that the impact will be different depending on the gender of the workforce (i.e. who will be more affected)?” the vast majority of respondents supported that for all paradigm shifters, all genders would be equally affected in all time horizons.

Table 5 Impact of the advancement of the Paradigm Shifters on the genders of the workforce (Shipbuilding)

Paradigm shifters		Impact on the genders (Shipbuilding)				
		only male	only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	By the year 2025	2%	6%	47%	4%	40%
	From year 2025 to 2030		2%	40%	9%	49%
	From year 2030 and beyond		2%	28%	4%	66%
Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources	By the year 2025	2%	2%	40%	2%	53%
	From year 2025 to 2030	2%		33%	5%	60%
	From year 2030 and beyond	2%		21%	2%	74%
Digitalization	By the year 2025	2%		26%	5%	67%
	From year 2025 to 2030			19%	5%	76%
	From year 2030 and beyond			12%	2%	86%
3D printing	By the year 2025	5%	3%	24%	3%	66%
	From year 2025 to 2030	3%		21%	3%	74%
	From year 2030 and beyond	3%		16%		82%
Green retrofitting	By the year 2025	3%		38%	3%	57%
	From year 2025 to 2030			27%	3%	70%
	From year 2030 and beyond			19%		81%
Drones	By the year 2025		5%	20%	5%	70%
	From year 2025 to 2030			10%	10%	80%
	From year 2030 and beyond			10%	5%	85%

8.2.1.8 1st Delphi Round, Question No.9 (out of 12)

“WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE? (free text answer)

In relation to the question “What are the new jobs that will emerge?” a very large percentage of the respondents declared that they did not know what new jobs would emerge. The level of uncertainty increased as the time horizon moved to the future. This question did not converge, so it was refined and used in the 2nd round.

8.2.1.9 1st Delphi Round, Question No.10 (out of 12)

“WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE? (Multi-select question)

In relation to the question “What would be the required skills and competences for the jobs that will emerge?” the vast majority of the Delphi respondents supported that for all paradigm shifters and for all time horizons, the following would be the required skills for the jobs that would emerge:

- Engineering Skills and
- Transferable Skills

Table 6 Required skills and competences for the jobs that will emerge per Paradigm Shifter (Shipbuilding)

Paradigm shifters		Required skills and competences (Shipbuilding)		
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics		Engineering skills	Health & safety skills	Transferable skills
	By the year 2025	77%	47%	66%
	From year 2025 to 2030	70%	38%	81%
	From year 2030 and beyond	62%	34%	74%
Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources		Engineering skills	Health & safety skills	Transferable skills
	By the year 2025	79%	56%	51%
	From year 2025 to 2030	65%	53%	67%
	From year 2030 and beyond	58%	44%	70%
Digitalization		Engineering skills	Health & safety skills	Transferable skills
	By the year 2025	74%	29%	55%
	From year 2025 to 2030	69%	43%	76%
	From year 2030 and beyond	69%	33%	69%
3D printing		Engineering skills	Health & safety skills	Transferable skills
	By the year 2025	63%	34%	45%
	From year 2025 to 2030	68%	32%	55%
	From year 2030 and beyond	58%	26%	61%

	Engineering skills	Health & safety skills	Transferable skills
Green retrofitting	By the year 2025	51%	51%
	From year 2025 to 2030	43%	65%
	From year 2030 and beyond	46%	54%

	Engineering skills	Health & safety skills	Transferable skills
Drones	By the year 2025	50%	40%
	From year 2025 to 2030	40%	60%
	From year 2030 and beyond	35%	70%

8.2.1.10 1st Delphi Round, Question No.11 (out of 12)

“HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?” (Multi-select question)

In relation to the question “How would the adversely affected workforce be retrained in order to catch up with the new development and remain employable in the same sector?” the training “Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer” and “Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE institutes etc.)” gathered the vast majority of respondents’ opinions for all PSs and all time horizons. The only exception was the *Digitalization* PS, in which the preferred option was “Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)” for all time horizons.

Table 7 How to retrain the affected workforce to remain employable in the same sector (Shipbuilding)

Paradigm shifters	How to retrain the affected workforce to remain employable in the same sector (Shipbuilding)		
	Attend a higher education course	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer	Vocational training (VET) by other providers
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	By the year 2025	34%	70%
	From year 2025 to 2030	38%	77%
	From year 2030 and beyond	49%	77%

	Attend a higher education course	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer	Vocational training (VET) by other providers
Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources	By the year 2025	40%	74%
	From year 2025 to 2030	44%	74%
	From year 2030 and beyond	51%	70%

Digitalization

	Attend a higher education course	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer	Vocational training (VET) by other providers
By the year 2025	60%	52%	48%
From year 2025 to 2030	64%	36%	55%
From year 2030 and beyond	62%	38%	60%

3D printing

	Attend a higher education course	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer	Vocational training (VET) by other providers
By the year 2025	37%	50%	42%
From year 2025 to 2030	39%	53%	55%
From year 2030 and beyond	42%	53%	50%

Green retrofitting

	Attend a higher education course	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer	Vocational training (VET) by other providers
By the year 2025	27%	46%	54%
From year 2025 to 2030	35%	57%	62%
From year 2030 and beyond	41%	54%	57%

Drones

	Attend a higher education course	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer	Vocational training (VET) by other providers
By the year 2025	20%	55%	40%
From year 2025 to 2030	25%	60%	60%
From year 2030 and beyond	45%	50%	60%

8.2.1.11 1st Delphi Round, Question No.12 (out of 12)

“WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?” (free text answer)

In relation to the question “What are the educational methods that would provide the new required skills more effectively (i.e. low cost, less training time, currently or not currently available educational and training programs etc.)?” the respondents provided input in open text format and proposed the following educational methods applicable to all paradigm shifters and for all horizons. This question was refined and used in the 2nd round.

Proposed educational methods (Shipbuilding)

- On the job training
- Online tutorials for self-training

- Innovation driven vocational training
- University new technology courses for engineers
- MOOC lifelong learning
- Educational programs with industry placements
- Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)
- Use of new technologies (AI methods, augmented reality, 3D applications)
- Modern methods (sensors, large data management techniques, artificial intelligence, problem solving, design and operation of autonomous ships and systems. advanced manufacturing skills, virtual reality)
- Training courses agreed with the workforce, their Unions and Employers
- Webinars combined with training on the job
- Online virtual reality courses

8.2.2 Results of the 2nd Delphi Round

8.2.2.1 2nd Delphi Round, Question No.1 (out of 4)

“IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER. PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED” (multi-select question)

During the 1st Delphi round, it was found that certain existing occupations would be affected by the advancement of the subject paradigm shifters. The participants of the 2nd Delphi round were asked to provide their views as to how these occupations would be affected. The vast majority of opinions showed that all affected occupations would require re-training and none would disappear. Details for the affected occupations and for all PSs are shown in the table below.

Table 8. How would the existing occupations be affected by the advancement of the Paradigm Shifters (Shipbuilding)

Paradigm shifters		EXISTING AFFECTED OCCUPATIONS AND HOW THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED (Shipbuilding)			
		Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	Naval architect	77%	35%	2%	2%
	Electromechanical engineer	67%	63%	2%	Na
	Electromechanical equipment assembler	63%	58%	2%	Na
	Marine engineer	74%	35%	5%	5%
	Electromechanical engineering technician	72%	51%	na	2%
	Electronics engineering technician	70%	60%	na	Na
	Marine electronics technician	60%	63%	2%	2%
	Electronic equipment assembler	56%	58%	14%	na
	Welder	42%	19%	56%	5%
	Boilermaker	30%	16%	58%	9%

Pipe welder (pipe fitter)	35%	19%	53%	9%
Sheet metal worker	30%	21%	58%	7%
Surface treatment operator	35%	26%	49%	7%
Abrasive blasting operator	33%	19%	56%	14%
Mobile crane operator	40%	23%	35%	12%
Production plant crane operator	42%	19%	35%	12%
Shipwright	44%	26%	30%	7%
Transport equipment painter	26%	23%	51%	12%

Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Marine engineering technician	81%	29%	10%	na
Marine engineering drafter	79%	14%	14%	2%
Marine engineer	74%	33%	7%	2%
Naval architect	74%	31%	10%	
Vessel engine assembler	69%	33%	14%	2%

Digitalization

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Marine engineering drafter	12%	41%	54%	7%
Electromechanical drafter	63%	24%	27%	2%
Electromechanical engineering technician	68%	41%	12%	na
Marine engineer	73%	27%	10%	2%
Marine engineering technician	71%	32%	15%	na
Electronics engineering technician	63%	46%	10%	Na
Electromechanical engineer	76%	37%	7%	Na
Marine electronics technician	61%	44%	10%	Na
Naval architect	80%	20%	10%	2%
Electromechanical equipment assembler	61%	44%	10%	2%
Electronic equipment assembler	59%	46%	10%	5%

3D printing

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Electromechanical engineering technician	78%	30%	10%	3%
Vessel engine assembler	73%	23%	18%	3%
Electromechanical equipment assembler	65%	28%	18%	3%
Computer numerical control (CNC) machine operator	58%	43%	18%	5%
Welder	40%	10%	50%	10%
Shipwright	53%	10%	35%	8%
Boilermaker	40%	10%	38%	15%
Pipe welder (pipe fitter)	48%	8%	40%	8%
Boat rigger	53%	18%	23%	15%

Green retrofitting

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Marine engineer	80%	30%	8%	3%
Naval architect	78%	28%	15%	Na
Marine engineering technician	75%	35%	15%	Na

Drones

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Vessel assembly supervisor	83%	18%	13%	Na
Vessel assembly inspector	78%	20%	23%	Na
Marine surveyor	83%	13%	18%	3%

8.2.2.2 2nd Delphi Round, Question No.2 (out of 4)

“IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING. IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT. IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW”. (Single-select question)

The Delphi participants of the 2nd round were presented with the results of the 1st round in relation to the question “what transferable skills would the adversely affected workforce need to have in order to be employable in a different job type/sector” and were asked to provide their answers as to what are the three (3) most important transferable skills. The participants agreed with the results of the 1st round as previously described in section 8.2.1.5 - Table 3.

8.2.2.3 2nd Delphi Round, Question No.3 (out of 4)

“THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.” (Single-select question)

From the 1st Delphi round, the respondents suggested a number of emerging occupations (i.e. new occupations as well as some existing ones that would gain relevance by the advancement of paradigm shifters considered). In the 2nd round, those emerging occupations were presented to the participants who were asked to provide their opinions as to whether those occupations would actually emerge. The opinions came to a clear consensus, showing that all of the occupations considered would actually emerge. The Table below shows the emerging occupations that were marked above 75%.

EXISTING occupation is considered to be the occupation that is already referred to in the ESCO database with the same name used in the Delphi **or** it is similar to other occupation(s) with similar descriptors that is (are) already referred to in the ESCO database.

NEW occupation is considered to be the occupation that is **neither** referred to in the ESCO database with the same name used in the Delphi **nor** is (are) occupation(s) with similar descriptors already referred to in the ESCO database.

The last column of the following Table indicates if the subject occupation has been considered as primary or supporting in the Baseline Report³ on present skills needs (which means that it is relevant for the subject sector in 2019).

Table 9 Emerging occupations⁴ per Paradigm Shifter (Shipbuilding).

Paradigm shifters	EMERGING OCCUPATIONS - NEW AND EXISTING THAT GAIN RELEVANCE (Shipbuilding)				
		% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	Innovation management [EXISTING]	84.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	Research and development manager	No
	Robotics (technician, operator, engineer, repair engineer) [EXISTING]	98.0%	Robotics engineer Robotics Engineer technician Industrial robot controller		Yes
	Mechatronics (engineer) [EXISTING]	79.0%	Mechatronics engineer		Yes
	Vessel automation (sensor technician,	98.0%	Automation engineer		Yes

³ Sdoukopoulos, E. et al. (2020). Baseline Report on present skills needs in shipbuilding and offshore renewables value chains. Results of the MATES project (www.projectmates.eu)

⁴ The occupations (OCC) are listed with the title proposed by experts during the first Delphi round. They are considered as EXISTING if there is a similar OCC defined in ESCO, and NEW when there is not any similar OCC in ESCO. The last column indicates if the OCC has been considered as one of the primary or supporting occupations for the sector in the Baseline Report on present skills needs.

marine automation technician, automation engineer) [EXISTING]		Automation engineering technician		
Vessel autonomy (fleet manager, operator, system engineer) [NEW]	84.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	N/A	No
Cyber-security (officer) [EXISTING]	93.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	ICT resilience manager, ICT security technician, ICT security Manager, ICT security administrator, ICT security consultant	Yes: ICT resilience manager

Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources

	% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
Energy management (planner, infrastructure engineer) [EXISTING]	95.0%	Energy manager		No
Alternative fuels (fuel cell engineer) [NEW]	93.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	No	No

Digitalization

	% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
(Big) data (manager, analyst) [EXISTING]	95.0%	Data analyst	knowledge engineer	Yes (Data analyst)
Cyber-security (officer) [EXISTING]	98.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	ICT resilience manager, ICT security technician, ICT security Manager, ICT security administrator, ICT security consultant	Yes: ICT resilience manager

3D printing

	% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
3D-printing (operator) [EXISTING]	93.0%	3D printing technician		No

Green retrofitting

	% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
Innovation management [EXISTING]	78.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	Research and development manager	No

Drones

	% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
Innovation management [EXISTING]	75.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	Research and development manager	No

8.2.2.4 2nd Delphi Round, Question No.4 (out of 4)

“FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE THE WORKFORCE WITH THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.”(Single-select question)

From the 1st Delphi round, it was found that a certain list of educational methods would provide the workforce with the new required skills more effectively. In the 2nd round of the Delphi exercise, the participants were asked to focus on the suitability of those methods with respect to the type of affected occupations identified earlier in the process. The results showed a consensus of opinions towards educational methods suitable for all affected occupations, highlighting the need for the lifelong learning approach and the use of webinars combined with training on the job. The following Table shows the pertinent results per paradigm shifter.

Table 10 Educational methods providing the workforce with the new required skills more effectively (Shipbuilding)

Paradigm shifters	EDUCATIONAL METHODS PROVIDING THE WORKFORCE WITH THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (Shipbuilding)			
		Suitable for all affected occupations	More suitable for affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable for affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	Higher education new technology courses	42.0%	33.0%	26.0%
	Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	44.0%	51.0%	5.0%
	Innovation driven vocational training	47.0%	37.0%	16.0%
	Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI), Augmented reality, 3D applications)	47.0%	33.0%	21.0%

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	51.0%	16.0%	33.0%
On the job training	53.0%	42.0%	5.0%
Educational programs with industry placements	60.0%	35.0%	5.0%
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	60.0%	26.0%	14.0%
Webinars combined with training on the job	67.0%	21.0%	12.0%
Life-long learning	81.0%	14.0%	5.0%

Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources

	Suitable to all affected occupations	More suitable to affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable to affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Innovation driven vocational training	43.0%	43.0%	14.0%
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	43.0%	48.0%	10.0%
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	45.0%	26.0%	29.0%
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	48.0%	38.0%	14.0%
Higher education new technology courses	50.0%	24.0%	26.0%
On the job training	57.0%	40.0%	2.0%
Educational programs with industry placements	62.0%	31.0%	7.0%
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	67.0%	29.0%	5.0%
Webinars combined with training on the job	71.0%	17.0%	12.0%
Life-long learning	88.0%	5.0%	7.0%

	Suitable for all affected occupations	More suitable for affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable for affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)

Digitalization

Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	41.0%	44.0%	15.0%
Innovation driven vocational training	44.0%	44.0%	12.0%
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	49.0%	32.0%	20.0%
Higher education new technology courses	51.0%	32.0%	17.0%
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	54.0%	37.0%	10.0%
Educational programs with industry placements	56.0%	39.0%	5.0%
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	59.0%	17.0%	24.0%
Webinars combined with training on the job	63.0%	15.0%	22.0%
On the job training	66.0%	29.0%	5.0%
Life-long learning	93.0%	5.0%	2.0%

3D printing

	Suitable for all affected occupations	More suitable for affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable for affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Higher education new technology courses	40.0%	38.0%	23.0%
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	40.0%	53.0%	8.0%
Innovation driven vocational training	43.0%	43.0%	15.0%
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	50.0%	35.0%	15.0%
On the job training	55.0%	38.0%	8.0%
Educational programs with industry placements	55.0%	35.0%	10.0%
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	55.0%	35.0%	10.0%
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	58.0%	20.0%	23.0%

Webinars combined with training on the job	68.0%	20.0%	13.0%
Life-long learning	88.0%	10.0%	3.0%

Green retrofitting

	Suitable for all affected occupations	More suitable for affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable for affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Higher education new technology courses	40.0%	35.0%	25.0%
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	45.0%	45.0%	10.0%
Innovation driven vocational training	48.0%	48.0%	5.0%
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	48.0%	33.0%	20.0%
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	55.0%	15.0%	30.0%
On the job training	60.0%	38.0%	3.0%
Educational programs with industry placements	60.0%	33.0%	8.0%
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	65.0%	30.0%	5.0%
Webinars combined with training on the job	75.0%	15.0%	10.0%
Life-long learning	85.0%	5.0%	10.0%

	Suitable for all affected occupations	More suitable for affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable for affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Higher education new technology courses	45.0%	33.0%	23.0%
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce,	48.0%	45.0%	8.0%

Drones

their unions and employers			
Innovation driven vocational training	53.0%	35.0%	13.0%
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	55.0%	28.0%	18.0%
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	58.0%	20.0%	23.0%
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	60.0%	35.0%	5.0%
Educational programs with industry placements	63.0%	30.0%	8.0%
On the job training	65.0%	33.0%	3.0%
Webinars combined with training on the job	65.0%	25.0%	10.0%
Life-long learning	85.0%	8.0%	8.0%

8.3 Offshore Renewable Energy

8.3.1 Results of the 1st Delphi Round

8.3.1.1 1st Delphi Round, Questions No.1 and No.3 (out of 12)

“WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?” (Rating scale question) and “IN WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?” (Single-select question)

In relation to the questions “Will this paradigm shifter become mainstream?” and “In which time horizon this paradigm shifter is likely to become mainstream?” the majority of the Delphi participants agreed that all of the paradigm shifters considered herein are expected to become mainstream by the year 2030 at the latest. The list of PSs below is in the order of their likelihood of becoming mainstream.

1. Smart grid & Smart sensors (yes: 82%)
2. Big data (yes: 81%)
3. Energy storage (yes: 81%)
4. Automation & Advanced robotics (yes: 79%)
5. 3D Printing (yes: 59%)

8.3.1.2 1st Delphi Round, Question No.2 (out of 12)

“WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?” (Rating scale question)

In relation to the question “Will this paradigm shifter affect (adversely or favourably) the current job situation in Europe?” the majority of the Delphi participants agreed that all PSs considered would have an effect as shown in the following list (in the order of their likelihood to affect the current job situation).

1. Smart grid & Smart sensors (yes: 70%)
2. Big data (yes: 69%)
3. Automation & Advanced robotics (yes: 67%)
4. Energy storage (yes: 58%)
5. 3D Printing (yes: 50%)

8.3.1.3 1st Delphi Round, Question No.4 (out of 12)

“HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?” (Single-select question)

In relation to the question “How would the current job situation be affected (adversely or favourably) by the advancement of the subject paradigm shifter?” the Delphi participants agreed that all Offshore Renewable Energy Paradigm Shifters are expected to affect the current job situation in Europe following the same trend, which is as follows:

- To be Slightly Affected to Affected by the year 2025
- To be Affected to Reshaped from year 2025 to 2030 and
- Reshaped to Fully Reshaped from year 2030 and beyond.

More than half of the expert respondents supported that the following paradigm shifters are expected to affect the current job situation in Europe from the current time and up to year 2025:

- 1) Automation and advanced robotics (55%)
- 2) Big data (54%)

Smart Grid and Smart Sensors followed with 42%.

8.3.1.4 1st Delphi Round, Question No.5 (out of 12)

“WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED?” (Multi-select question)

In relation to the question “What existing occupations will be most affected (adversely or favorably) and by when?” the Delphi participants agreed that the most affected occupations per PS are as shown in the following Table.

Table 11 Most affected occupations against predicted Paradigm Shifters (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Paradigm shifters	Most affected occupations
Automation and advanced robotics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cable installer - Tidal power technician - Electromechanical engineer technician - Other: Drone pilots and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) technicians
3D printing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welder - Wind turbine technician, and - Electromechanical Equipment assembler
Smart grid and smart sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Power distribution engineer - Electric power generation engineer - Maintenance and repair engineer
Big data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Renewable energy engineer - Energy systems engineer - Other: Hydrodynamicist, Management occupations
Energy storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Power production plant operator - Solar power plant operator

It was also shown that all of the PS considered are expected to have a big effect on the subject existing occupations during the time period of 2025-2030, except for *Big Data* that is expected to be effective even before the year 2025. The *Smart Grid and Smart Sensors* was shown to have some impact by the year 2025. *3D Printing* appears to be the only one with a relatively strong impact from year 2030 and beyond.

Table 12 Timeline: Effect of Paradigm shifters on existing occupations (Offshore Renewable Energy)

	<2025 (% responses)	2025-2030 (% responses)	>2030 (% responses)
Automation and advanced robotics	29%	48%	23%
3D Printing	20%	43%	36%
Smart Grid and Smart Sensors	39%	43%	18%
Big Data	44.5%	38%	17.5%
Energy Storage	32%	45.5%	22.3%

8.3.1.5 1st Delphi Round, Question No.6 (out of 12)

“WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?” (Multi-select question)

In relation to the question “What transferable skills should the adversely affected workforce have in order to be employable in a different job type/sector etc.?” the majority of responses (42% to 56%) support that the adversely affected workforce will need to have all of the transferable skills shown in the Table below by the year 2025. *Automation and Advanced Robotics* (56%) and *Big Data* (50%) gathered the vast majority of responses for the <2025 period.

Table 13 Timeline: Effect of Paradigm Shifters on transferable skills (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Paradigm shifters and transferable skills needed	<2025 (% responses)	2025-2030 (% responses)	>2030 (% responses)
Automation and advanced robotics	56%	29%	15%
3D Printing	43%	41%	16%
Smart Grid and Smart Sensors	48%	37%	15%
Big Data	50%	31%	18%
Energy Storage	42%	33%	25%

Table 14 Transferable skills that the adversely affected workforce should have (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Paradigm shifters	Transferable skills that the adversely affected workforce should have
Automation and advanced robotics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Flexibility and adaptability - Communication and collaboration
3D printing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and Technologies (ICT) Literacy Communication - Flexibility and adaptability - Critical thinking and problem-solving - Creative thinking and innovation
Smart grid and smart sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Flexibility and adaptability - Communication and collaboration - Critical thinking and problem-solving
Big data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Flexibility and adaptability - Initiative and self-direction
Energy storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Flexibility and adaptability - Communication and collaboration together with Creative thinking and innovation

The two most important skills for the workforce to have, that are consistent in all paradigm shifters, are:

- Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
- Flexibility and adaptability

8.3.1.6 1st Delphi Round, Question No.7 (out of 12)

“WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?” (Single-select question)

In relation to the question “What ages of the workforce would be most (adversely) affected and when?” the majority of responses support that:

- The ages above 55 years old will be the most adversely affected ages from year 2030 and beyond
- The ages up to 25 years old will be the least adversely affected in all time horizons
- All ages above 35 years old will be almost equally affected between years 2025-2030

Table 15 Ages of the workforce affected by the advancement of Paradigm Shifters (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Ages of workforce affected	Paradigm Shifter (Offshore Renewable Energy)				
	Automation and advanced robotics	3D Printing	Smart Grid and Smart Sensors	Big Data	Energy Storage
	<2025				
	(% respondents)				
Up to 25 years old	2%	3%	7%	3%	2%
25-35	19%	21%	12%	15%	17%
35-45	24%	32%	29%	28%	27%
45-55	19%	18%	24%	28%	27%
>55 years old	36%	26%	27%	28%	27%
	2025-2030				
	(% respondents)				
Up to 25 years old	7%	5%	2%	5%	2%
25-35	14%	24%	22%	13%	20%
35-45	31%	21%	24%	35%	29%
45-55	21%	26%	32%	28%	29%
>55 years old	26%	24%	20%	20%	20%
	>2030				
	(% respondents)				
Up to 25 years old	14%	13%	12%	18%	12%
25-35	17%	21%	15%	8%	12%
35-45	21%	13%	22%	23%	32%
45-55	14%	18%	22%	18%	17%
>55 years old	33%	34%	29%	35%	27%

8.3.1.7 1st Delphi Round, Question No.8 (out of 12)

“DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?” (Single-select question)

In relation to the question “Do you consider that the impact will be different depending on the gender of the workforce (i.e. who will be more affected)?” the vast majority of respondents supported that for all paradigm shifters, all genders would be equally affected in all time horizons.

Table 16 Impact of the advancement of the Paradigm Shifters on the genders of the workforce (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Paradigm shifters and genders	<2025 (% Male more than other – % Equally affected)	2025-2030 (% Male more than other – % Equally affected)	>2030 (% Male more than other – % Equally affected)
Automation and advanced robotics	29%-62%	29%-62%	17%-74%
3D Printing	21%-61%	24%-66%	11%-77%
Smart Grid and Smart Sensors	29%-54%	29%-61%	17%-76%
Big Data	23%-63%	20%-73%	10%-83%
Energy Storage	22%-71%	22%-78%	10%-80%

8.3.1.8 1st Delphi Round, Question No.9 (out of 12)

“WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE? (free text answer)

In relation to the question “What are the new jobs that will emerge?” a very large percentage of the respondents declared that they did not know what new jobs would emerge. The level of uncertainty increased as the time horizon went to the future. This question did not converge, so it was refined and used in the 2nd round.

8.3.1.9 1st Delphi Round, Question No.10 (out of 12)

“WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE? (Multi-select question)

In relation to the question “What would be the required skills and competences for the jobs that will emerge?” the vast majority of the Delphi respondents supported that for all paradigm shifters and for all time horizons, the following would be the required skills for the jobs that would emerge:

- Engineering Skills and
- Transferable Skills

Engineering Skills appear to dominate in most of the PSs considered, except for the Big Data paradigm shifter where Transferable Skills seem to be most required. Moreover, Transferable Skills are most

required for the *Energy Storage* >2025 horizon and for the *Smart Grid and Smart Sensors* >2030 horizon.

Table 17 Required skills and competences for the jobs that will emerge per Paradigm Shifter (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Paradigm Shifters and required skills	<2025 Engineering- Transferable- Health & Safety	2025-2030 Engineering- Transferable- Health & Safety	>2030 Engineering- Transferable- Health & Safety
Automation and advanced robotics	39%-35%-25%	38%-32%-29%	33%-33%-28%
3D Printing	46%-34%-17%	39%-32%-26%	38%-38%-20%
Smart Grid and Smart Sensors	41%-37%-18%	35%-33%-29%	34%-37%-22%
Big Data	41%-44%-15%	35%-42%-23%	36%-43%-16%
Energy Storage	36%-32%-23%	34%-38%-27%	35%-39%-22%

8.3.1.10 1st Delphi Round, Question No.11 (out of 12)

“HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?” (Multi-select question)

In relation to the question “How would the adversely affected workforce be retrained in order to catch up with the new development and remain employable in the same sector? The Delphi participants responded as follows:

In *Automation and advanced robotics* and *3D Printing* paradigm shifters:

- by year 2025: workforce is suggested to be retrained “Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current” and “Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE institutes etc.)”
- from year 2030 and beyond: workforce is suggested to be retrained “Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE institutes etc.)”.

In *Smart Grid and Smart Sensors*, and *Energy Storage*, the workforce is suggested to be retrained by “Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE institutes etc.)” in all time horizons.

In *Big Data* paradigm shifter:

- up to year 2030: workforce is suggested to be retrained by “attending a higher education course (i.e. at a university)”
- in all time horizons: workforce is suggested to be retrained “Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE institutes etc.)”

Table 18 How to retrain the affected workforce to remain employable in the same sector (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Paradigm Shifters and retraining of the workforce	<2025 Voc Current - Voc Other - Higher edu.	2025-2030 Voc Current - Voc Other - Higher edu.	>2030 Voc Current - Voc Other - Higher edu.
Automation and advanced robotics	39%-36%-20%	38%-42%-18%	25%-43%-26%
3D Printing	37%-37%-22%	38%-44%-18%	29%-45%-23%
Smart Grid and Smart Sensors	32%-38%-24%	30%-42%-27%	29%-41%-28%
Big Data	25%-34%-38%	27%-38%-34%	27%-39%-28%
Energy Storage	27%-34%-30%	29%-38%-29%	29%-37%-29%

8.3.1.11 1st Delphi Round, Question No.12 (out of 12)

“WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?” (free text answer)

In relation to the question “What are the educational methods that would provide the new required skills more effectively (i.e. low cost, less training time, currently or not currently available educational and training programs etc.)?” the respondents provided input in open text format and proposed the following educational methods applicable to all paradigm shifters and for all horizons. This question was refined and used in the 2nd round:

- On the job training
- Online tutorials for self-training
- Innovation driven vocational training
- University new technology courses for engineers
- MOOC lifelong learning
- Educational programs with industry placements
- Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)
- Use of new technologies (AI methods, augmented reality, 3D applications)
- Modern methods (sensors, large data management techniques, artificial intelligence, problem solving, design and operation of autonomous ships and systems. advanced manufacturing skills, virtual reality)
- Training courses agreed with the workforce, their Unions and Employers
- Webinars combined with training on the job
- Online virtual reality courses

8.3.2 Results of the 2nd Delphi Round

8.3.2.1 2nd Delphi Round, Question No.1 (out of 4)

“IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER. PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED”. (multi-select question)

During the 1st Delphi round, it was found that certain existing occupations would be affected by the advancement of the subject paradigm shifters. The respondents of the 2nd Delphi round were asked to provide their views as to how these occupations would be affected. The vast majority of opinions showed that the needs of all affected occupations would increase and re-training would be required. The only exception was the occupation of welder, for which the demand would decrease and would require re-training (see Table below).

Table 19 How would the existing occupations be affected by the advancement of the Paradigm Shifters (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Paradigm shifters	EXISTING AFFECTED OCCUPATIONS AND HOW THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED (Offshore Renewable Energy)				
		Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Automation and advanced robotics	Cable installer	50%	47%	21%	5%
	Tidal power technician	47%	58%	11%	na
	Electromechanical engineering technician	53%	61%	5%	na
	Wave power technician	47%	74%	8%	na
	Wind turbine technician	50%	68%	5%	na
	Electromechanical equipment assembler	50%	50%	16%	3%
	Welder	50%	18%	37%	3%
	Maintenance and repair engineer	68%	34%	13%	na
	Construction commercial diver	45%	42%	24%	5%
	Electronic equipment assembler	55%	45%	11%	na
	Solar energy technician	47%	63%	5%	na
Hydropower technician	42%	63%	13%	na	
3D printing	Welder	54%	16%	38%	5%
	Wave power technician	54%	51%	14%	na
	Electromechanical equipment assembler	54%	32%	27%	3%
	Wind turbine technician	57%	59%	8%	na
	Tidal power technician	51%	59%	11%	na
	Solar energy technician	51%	59%	11%	na
	Hydropower technician	49%	62%	16%	na
	Electromechanical engineering technician	54%	49%	16%	na
Electronic equipment assembler	51%	43%	22%	3%	

Printed circuit board assembler	54%	43%	11%	5%
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Smart grid and smart sensors

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Power distribution engineer	68%	46%	8%	na
Electric power generation engineer	65%	49%	8%	na
Maintenance and repair engineer	65%	43%	14%	na
Power production plant operator	68%	43%	5%	3%
Solar power plant operator	57%	54%	5%	3%

Big data

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Renewable energy engineer	62%	54%		3%
Energy systems engineer	54%	62%	3%	na
Wind energy engineer	49%	65%	3%	na
Power distribution engineer	59%	54%	8%	na
Power production plant operator	62%	46%	11%	3%
Electric power generation engineer	68%	41%	8%	3%
Maintenance and repair engineer	70%	32%	14%	na
Wind turbine technician	51%	62%	8%	na
Solar energy engineer	49%	57%	11%	na
Solar energy technician	54%	57%	11%	na
Solar power plant operator	54%	51%	14%	na
Hydropower technician	38%	59%	19%	na
Wave power technician	54%	70%	5%	na
Tidal power technician	54%	65%	5%	na

Energy storage

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Power production plant operator	62%	54%	8%	na
Solar power plant operator	51%	65%	8%	na
Power distribution engineer	65%	59%	3%	na
Electric power generation engineer	68%	54%	3%	na
Maintenance and repair engineer	65%	54%	5%	na

8.3.2.2 2nd Delphi Round, Question No.2 (out of 4)

“IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING. IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT. IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW”. (Single-select question)

The Delphi participants of the 2nd round were presented the results of the 1st round in relation to the question “what transferable skills would the adversely affected workforce need to have in order to be employable in a different job type/sector” and were asked to provide their answers as to what are the three (3) most important transferable skills. The participants agreed with the results of the 1st round as previously described in section 8.3.1.5 - Table 14.

8.3.2.3 2nd Delphi Round, Question No.3 (out of 4)

“THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.” (Single-select question)

From the 1st Delphi round, the respondents suggested a number of emerging occupations (i.e. new occupation as well as some existing ones that would gain relevance by the advancement of paradigm shifters considered). In the 2nd round, those emerging occupations were presented to the participants who were asked to provide their opinions as to whether those occupations would actually emerge. The opinions came to a clear consensus, showing that all of the occupations considered would actually emerge. The Table below shows the emerging occupations that were marked above 75%.

EXISTING occupation is considered to be the occupation that is already referred to in the ESCO database with the same name used in the Delphi or it is similar with other occupation(s) with similar descriptors that is (are) already in the ESCO database.

NEW occupation is considered to be the occupation that is neither referred to in the ESCO database with the same name used in the Delphi nor is (are) occupation(s) with similar descriptors already in the ESCO database.

The last column of the following Table indicates if the subject occupation has been considered as primary or supporting in the Baseline Report⁵ on present skills needs (which means that it is relevant for the subject sector in 2019).

Table 20 Emerging⁶ occupations per Paradigm Shifter (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Paradigm shifters	EMERGING OCCUPATIONS -NEW AND EXISTING THAT GAIN RELEVANCE (Offshore Renewable Energy)				
		% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
Automation and advanced robotics	Sustainability engineer (EXISTING)	76.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	Process engineering technician	No
	Mechatronics technician (EXISTING)	79.0%	Mechatronics engineering technician		Yes

⁵ Sdoukopoulos, E. et al. (2020). Baseline Report on present skills needs in shipbuilding and offshore renewables value chains. Results of the MATES project (www.projectmates.eu)

⁶ The occupations (OCC) are listed with the title proposed by experts during the first Delphi round. They are considered as EXISTING if there is a similar OCC defined in ESCO, and NEW when there is not any similar OCC in ESCO. The last column indicates if the OCC has been considered as one of the primary or supporting occupations for the sector in the Baseline Report on present skills needs.

Paradigm shifters **EMERGING OCCUPATIONS -NEW AND EXISTING THAT GAIN RELEVANCE (Offshore Renewable Energy)**

Predictive maintenance analyst (EXISTING)	84.0%		Industrial maintenance supervisor	Yes
Big Data manager (EXISTING)	92.0%	chief data officer	Data analyst	No (Data analyst)
Virtual Reality (VR) designer (EXISTING)	92.0%	3D modeler		No (but includes Design engineer)
Cyber security expert (EXISTING)	92.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	ICT resilience manager , ICT security technician , ICT security Manager, ICT security administrator, ICT security consultant	Yes: ICT resilience manager
Drone and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) pilot-operator (NEW)	95.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi	No	No
Artificial Intelligence (AI) professional (EXISTING)	95.0%	ICT intelligent systems designer		No
Robotics (constructor, programmer, operator) (EXISTING)	97.0%	Robotics engineer , Robotics Engineer technician , Industrial robot controller		Yes
Autonomous system operator (EXISTING)	97.0%	N/A as it is named in Delphi: automation engineering technician has the "Automation engineering assistant" as alternative title	Automation engineer Automation engineering technician	Yes

3D printing

	% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
3D printer maintenance worker (EXISTING)	84.0%		3D printing technician	No
Designer of parts for 3D	92.0%	3D modeler		No (but includes Design engineer)

Paradigm shifters **EMERGING OCCUPATIONS -NEW AND EXISTING THAT GAIN RELEVANCE (Offshore Renewable Energy)**

printing (EXISTING)				
3D printing (technician, engineer, expert) (EXISTING)	97.0%	3D printing technician		No

Smart grid and smart sensors

	% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
Artificial Intelligence (AI) professional (EXISTING)	89.0%	ICT intelligent systems designer		No
Remote controller (NEW)	92.0%	No		No
Sensors (developer, installer, technician) (EXISTING)	95.0%	Sensor engineer		No
Big Data analyst (EXISTING)	97.0%	Data analyst		Yes

Big data

	% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
Big Data systems (developer, engineer) (EXISTING)	100.0%	knowledge engineer database developer		No

Energy storage

	% respondents	ESCO	ESCO similar	Primary/supporting OCC 2019
Grid Insulation and Construction professional (EXISTING)	78.0%		Insulation supervisor Underwater construction supervisor Construction general supervision	No
Energy storage specialist (EXISTING)	95.0%	energy systems engineer which has the alternative label "Energy storage systems engineer"		Yes

8.3.2.4 2nd Delphi Round, Question No.4 (out of 4)

“FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE THE WORKFORCE WITH THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.” (Single-select question)

From the 1st Delphi round, it was found that a certain list of educational methods would provide the workforce with the new required skills more effectively. In the 2nd round of the Delphi exercise, the participants were asked to focus on the suitability of those methods with respect to the type of affected occupations identified earlier in the process. The results showed a consensus of opinions towards educational methods suitable to all affected occupations, highlighting the need for lifelong learning approach and the use of webinars combined with training on the job. The following table shows the pertinent results per paradigm shifter.

Table 21 Educational methods to provide to the workforce the new required skills more effectively (Offshore Renewable Energy)

Paradigm shifters	EDUCATIONAL METHODS TO PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (Offshore Renewable Energy)	
Automation and advanced robotics		% respondents
	Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	37.0%
	Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	45.0%
	Innovation driven vocational training	47.0%
	On the job training	50.0%
	Educational programs with industry placements	53.0%
	Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	58.0%
	Higher education new technology courses	63.0%
	Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	71.0%
	Webinars combined with training on the job	71.0%
	Life-long learning	92.0%
3D printing		% respondents
	Innovation driven vocational training	35.0%
	Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	35.0%
	Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	51.0%
	On the job training	51.0%
	Educational programs with industry placements	51.0%
	Higher education new technology courses	54.0%
	Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	54.0%
	Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	59.0%
	Webinars combined with training on the job	59.0%
Life-long learning	84.0%	

Paradigm shifters	EDUCATIONAL METHODS TO PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (Offshore Renewable Energy)	
Smart grid and smart sensors		% respondents
	Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	46.0%
	Innovation driven vocational training	51.0%
	Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	54.0%
	Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	59.0%
	On the job training	59.0%
	Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	62.0%
	Higher education new technology courses	65.0%
	Educational programs with industry placements	65.0%
	Webinars combined with training on the job	68.0%
	Life-long learning	86.0%
Big data		% respondents
	Innovation driven vocational training	49.0%
	Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	51.0%
	Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	54.0%
	On the job training	54.0%
	Educational programs with industry placements	57.0%
	Higher education new technology courses	62.0%
	Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	65.0%
	Webinars combined with training on the job	65.0%
	Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	70.0%
Life-long learning	89.0%	
Energy storage		% respondents
	Higher education new technology courses	46.0%
	On the job training	49.0%
	Innovation driven vocational training	49.0%
	Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	49.0%
	Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	54.0%
	Educational programs with industry placements	57.0%
	Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	59.0%
	Webinars combined with training on the job	68.0%
	Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	68.0%
Life-long learning	86.0%	

9 Conclusion and Comments

The trends and driving forces dealt with and identified during the Delphi survey are foreseen to affect the employability of the Shipbuilding and Offshore Renewable Energy sectors, making it necessary for all professionals to adapt to the new developments by following dynamic and lifelong approaches with shorter turnarounds.

The subject Delphi exercise revealed a large number of interesting points that are summarized below and ask for immediate action to be taken, starting from the PSs that would first become mainstream. The following two Figures illustrate a representation of the periods (time horizons) in which the Delphi respondents consider that each paradigm shifter would become mainstream along with key findings on the associated employment landscape (i.e. showing the main affected occupations as well as the anticipated emerging occupations; Rankings shown are based on the percentage of Delphi respondents in agreement). More details are provided in the subsequent sections 9.1 to 9.5 and Tables 23 and 24.

Figure 9. Shipbuilding sector: *Future scenarios with key findings*: <https://www.projectmates.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/MATES-Strategy-Report-Sep-2019.pdf>

Agreement on the impact in jobs
 >50% >60% >70%

Figure10. Shipbuilding sector: Future scenarios with key findings: <https://www.projectmates.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/MATES-Strategy-Report-Sep-2019.pdf>

9.1 Timeline of Paradigm Shifters

9.1.1 Shipbuilding

All of the Shipbuilding Paradigm Shifters considered would become mainstream by the year 2030 and appear to have the following hierarchical order (no.1 would become mainstream first):

1) Green retrofitting (years 2019-2025), 2) Digitalization (years 2019-2030), 3) Drones (years 2019-2030), 4) Vessel automation, autonomy and advanced robotics (years 2025-2030), 5) Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources (years 2025-2030), 6) 3D Printing (years 2025-2030).

According to the opinions of the Delphi participants, the PS *Green Retrofitting* appears to emerge earlier and has a shorter “life cycle” compared to the other PSs. This could be attributed to the fact that the subject PS concerns existing vessels and the activities related to their compliance with new legislations and it would be expected that all (existing vessels) would eventually become compliant by the year 2025 (e.g. IMO’s requirements on low carbon shipping and air pollution control emission reduction etc. - <http://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/HotTopics/GHG/Pages/default.aspx>).

PSs like *Digitalization* and *Vessel automation, autonomy and advanced robotics* have already started becoming mainstream and they will become fully developed by the year 2030. For example, there is already a market of fully developed remotely operated patrol boats that are controlled and operated from another location, without seafarers on board (<https://www.iai.co.il/p/katana>).

It is considered that all of the PSs, apart from the Green Retrofitting would maintain their status as “mainstream” even beyond the year 2030.

Table 22 Timeline of Paradigm Shifters sorted by: 1st) their likelihood to become mainstream 2nd) how much would they affect the job situation in Europe (Shipbuilding)

Paradigm shifters	Will it become mainstream?	Time horizon in which it would become mainstream	Will it affect the job situation?
Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics	87%	2025-2030	79%
Digitalization	87%	2019-2030	75%
Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources	83%	2025-2030	67%
Drones	73%	2019-2030	55%
Green retrofitting	70%	2019-2025	50%
3D printing	59%	2025-2030	52%

9.1.2 Offshore renewable energy

All of the offshore renewable energy paradigm shifters considered herein would become mainstream by the year 2030 and appear to have the following hierarchical order (no.1 would become mainstream first):

1) Big Data (years 2019-2025), 2) Automation and advanced robotics (years 2019-2025), 3) Smart grid and Smart sensors (years 2019-2030), 4) Energy storage (years 2025-2030), 5) 3D Printing (years 2025-2030).

It is considered that all of the PSs considered, apart from the *Big Data* would maintain their status as “mainstream” even beyond the year 2030.

Table 23 Timeline of Paradigm Shifters sorted by: 1st) their likelihood to become mainstream 2nd) how much would they affect the job situation in Europe (Offshore renewable energy)

Paradigm shifters	Will it become mainstream?	Time horizon in which it would become mainstream	Will it affect the job situation?
Smart grid and smart sensors	82%	2019-2030	70%
Big data	81%	2019-2025	69%
Energy storage	81%	2025-2030	58%
Automation and advanced robotics	79%	2019-2025	67%
3D printing	59%	2025-2030	50%

9.2 Affected occupations and the way they would be affected

9.2.1 Shipbuilding

The majority of the Delphi participants agreed that all PSs considered would affect (adversely or favourably) the current job situation in Europe in the same order as their likelihood to become mainstream (No.1 PS would affect the current job situation the most): 1) Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics 2) Digitalization, 3) Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources, 4) Drones, 5) 3D Printing, 6) Green retrofitting.

Further analysis of the collected data showed that all genders of the workforce would be equally affected in all of the time horizons considered (i.e. from years 2019-2025, from years 2025-2030, beyond year 2030).

The ages that would become more affected in the short term (i.e. from 2019 to 2025) are those from 35 years old and above. In the longer term (i.e. from years 2025 to 2030), the most affected ages appear to be those from 35 to 55 years old. In all time horizons (and all PS’s), the younger workforce (i.e. below 25 years old) appears to remain unaffected. An interesting finding was that the PS *Drones*, would affect almost all ages from 25 years old and above in all time horizons.

The workforce in the vast majority of the affected occupations (apart from only one occupation) would require retraining in order to remain employable. The Delphi exercise revealed that almost half (57%) of the affected occupations would experience an increase in demand and around 30% of them would face a decrease in demand. Five (5) occupations did not collect enough evidence on which to draw conclusions (PS Drones: Vessel assembly supervisor, Vessel assembly inspector, Marine surveyor; PS Digitalization: Electromechanical drafter; PS Exploitation of alternative fuels: Marine engineering drafter). An important finding was that, according to the majority of the collected opinions, none of the affected occupations would disappear.

9.2.2 Offshore renewable energy

The majority of the Delphi participants agreed that all PSs considered would affect (adversely or favourably) the current job situation in Europe in the same order as their likelihood to become mainstream (No.1 PS would affect the current job situation the most):

1) Smart grid and smart sensors, 2) Big data, 3) Automation and advanced robotics, 4) Energy storage, 5) 3D Printing.

Further analysis of the collected data showed that all genders of the workforce would be equally affected in all of the time horizons considered.

The landscape for the ages of the workforce and the affected occupations is similar to the Shipbuilding sector. Namely, the ages that would become more affected in the short term (i.e. from 2019 to 2025) are those from 35 years old and above. In the longer term (i.e. from years 2025 to 2030), the most affected ages appear to be those from 35 to 55 years old. From year 2030 and beyond, ages from 55 years old and above appear to be affected the most. In all time horizons (and all PSs), the younger workforce (i.e. below 25 years old) appears to remain unaffected.

The workforce in all of the affected occupations would require retraining in order to remain employable. It was recorded that the vast majority (96%) of the affected occupations would experience an increase in demand. According to the majority of the collected opinions, none of the affected occupations would disappear.

9.3 Required skills and competences

9.3.1 Shipbuilding

It was clearly shown that transferable skills would be very important as a means of addressing the emerging skills gaps produced by all paradigm shifters. The majority of the respondents' opinions supported that the most important skills and competences for the workforce to have by the year 2025 would be: a) Engineering Skills and b) Transferable Skills. Their importance would remain high in the longer term (i.e. from year 2025 and beyond) where the Health & safety skills also become important. The two most important transferable skills for the workforce to have in all time horizons would be: a) Critical thinking and problem-solving, b) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy.

9.3.2 Offshore renewable energy

The landscape on the most important skills and competences in the offshore renewable energy sector appears to be similar to that of the shipbuilding sector. A slight difference is that the two most important transferable skills for the workforce to have in all time horizons would be: a) Flexibility and adaptability, b) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy.

9.4 Most effective training and educational methods

9.4.1 Shipbuilding

The majority of the Delphi participants agreed that Vocational Training (VET) delivered by the current employer would be the most effective training method to provide the required skills and competences to the affected workforce in the short-term horizon (i.e. up to year 2025). For the mid and long-term horizons (i.e. from years 2025 to 2030 and beyond) it would be VET provided by the combination of current and other providers.

The most effective educational methods that gathered the majority of opinions were the: a) lifelong learning, b) webinars combined with training on the job.

9.4.2 Offshore renewable energy

The Delphi respondents agree that the training offered from other providers will have a great importance (greater than in the shipbuilding sector). It was shown that both VET options (i.e. VET from current employer and other providers) will be suitable for the majority of paradigm shifters in the short term (i.e. up to year 2025), and the VET offered by other providers will be the most popular in all paradigm shifters in the mid and long-term horizons (i.e. from years 2025 to 2030 and beyond).

9.5 Expected emerging occupations

9.5.1 Shipbuilding

The respondents, for the shipbuilding sector, suggested fourteen (14) emerging occupations, from which 57% were existing occupations that would gain relevance by the advancement of paradigm shifters considered and 43% may be classified as new occupations.

9.5.2 Offshore renewable energy

The respondents, for the offshore renewable energy, suggested twenty-two (22) emerging occupations, from which 45% were existing occupations that would gain relevance by the advancement of paradigm shifters and 55% may be classified as new occupations.

Table 24 Paradigm shifters in 3-time horizons and associated future scenarios on occupations (existing and new), skills, competences and training needs for the Shipbuilding sector (in the order of which will become mainstream first).

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Shipbuilding)			Affected occupation and way they would be affected				Required skills and competences		Most effective training methods		Most effective educational methods		Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)	
2019	2025	2030		Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease								
<p>-Will become mainstream?: YES, Ranked 1st with 87% -Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked 2nd with 75% -All genders would be equally affected - Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected: a) <2025: 35 years old and above b) from 2025 to 2030: 35 years old and above c) >2030: equally all ages from 55 years old and above</p>			Marine engineering drafter	YES	NO	YES	Engineering skills & Transferable skills	By the year 2025	Attend a higher education course	Educational programs with industry placements	56.0%	(Big) data (manager, analyst) [EXISTING]	95%	
			Electromechanical drafter	YES	NO	NO		From year 2025 to 2030		From year 2025 to 2030	Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	59.0%	Cyber-security (officer) [NEW]	98%
			Electromechanical engineering technician	YES	YES	NO		From year 2030 and beyond		From year 2030 and beyond	Webinars combined with training on the job	63.0%		
			Marine engineer	YES	YES	NO				On the job training	66.0%			
			Marine engineering technician	YES	YES	NO				Life-long learning	93.0%			
			Electronics engineering technician	YES	YES	NO								
			Electromechanical engineer	YES	YES	NO								
			Marine electronics technician	YES	YES	NO								
			Naval architect	YES	YES	NO								
			Electromechanical equipment assembler	YES	YES	NO								
Electronic equipment assembler	YES	YES	NO											

Most important Transferable skills:
 -Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
 -Creative thinking and innovation
 -Critical thinking and problem solving

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Shipbuilding)			Affected occupation and way they would be affected				Required skills and competences		Most effective training methods		Most effective educational methods		Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)		
2019	2025	2030		Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	By the year 2025	Engineering skills	By the year 2025	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer					
 Drones							By the year 2025	Engineering skills	By the year 2025	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer	Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	60.0%	Innovation management [EXISTING]	75%	
			Vessel assembly supervisor	YES	NO	NO	From year 2025 to 2030	Transferable skills	From year 2025 to 2030	Vocational training (VET) by other providers	Educational programs with industry placements	63.0%			
			Vessel assembly inspector	YES	NO	NO	From year 2030 and beyond		From year 2030 and beyond		On the job training	65.0%			
			Marine surveyor	YES	NO	NO					Webinars combined with training on the job	65.0%			
											Life-long learning	85.0%			

-Will become mainstream?: YES, Ranked 4th with 73%
 -Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked 4th with 55%
 -All genders would be equally affected
 - Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected:
 a) <2025: Slightly ages 25-35 years old, but mainly ages from 55 and above
 b) from 2025 to 2030: Equally all ages from 25 years old and above.
 c) >2030: ages 25-35 years old and also ages from 45 years old and above

Most important Transferable skills:
 -Flexibility and adaptability
 -Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
 -Critical thinking and problem solving

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Shipbuilding)			Affected occupation and way they would be affected			Required skills and competences		Most effective training methods		Most effective educational methods		Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)			
2019	2025	2030		Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	By the year 2025	Engineering skills, Health & safety skills & Transferable skills	By the year 2025	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer & by other providers	On the job training	60.0%	Innovation management [EXISTING]	78%	
			Marine engineer	YES	YES	NO	From year 2025 to 2030	Health & safety skills & Transferable skills	From year 2025 to 2030		60.0%	Educational programs with industry placements			60.0%
			Naval architect	YES	YES	NO	From year 2030 and beyond		From year 2030 and beyond			Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)			
			Marine engineering technician	YES	YES	NO			Webinars combined with training on the job	75.0%					
							Most important Transferable skills: -Flexibility and adaptability -Knowledge management and transfer -Critical thinking and problem solving				Life-long learning	85.0%			

Will become mainstream?:
 YES, Ranked 5th with 70%
 -Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked last (6th) with 50%
 -All genders would be equally affected
 - Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected:
 a) <2025: 35 years old and above
 b) from 2025 to 2030: Mainly 35-45 years old, and also ages above 55.
 c) >2030: slightly ages 25-45 years old and mainly ages from 55 and above

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Shipbuilding)			Affected occupation and way they would be affected			Required skills and competences	Most effective training methods		Most effective educational methods		Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)					
2019	2025	2030		Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease										
<p style="text-align: center;">Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics</p> <p>-Will become mainstream?: YES, Ranked 1st with 87% -Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked 1st with 79% -All genders would be equally affected - Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected: a) <2025: 45 years old and above b) from 2025 to 2030: 35 years old to 55 c) >2030: equally all ages from 25 years old and above</p>							By the year 2025 From year 2025 to 2030 From year 2030 and beyond	Engineering skills & Transferable skills	By the year 2025 Vocational training (VET) by the current employer	On the job training 53.0%	Mechatronics (engineer) [EXISTING] 79 %	Innovation management [EXISTING] 84 %				
			Naval architect	YES	YES	NO							Most important Transferable skills: - Critical thinking and problem solving - Communication and collaboration - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	From year 2025 to 2030 Vocational training (VET) by the current employer & other providers	Educational programs with industry placements 60.0%	Vessel autonomy (fleet manager, operator, system engineer) [NEW] 84 %
			Electromechanical engineer	YES	YES	NO										
			Electromechanical equipment assembler	YES	YES	NO	From year 2030 and beyond Vocational training (VET) by other providers	Webinars combined with training on the job 67.0%	Robotics (technician, operator, engineer, repair engineer) [NEW] 98 %							
			Marine engineer	YES	YES	NO	From year 2030 and beyond Vocational training (VET) by other providers	Life-long learning 81.0%	Vessel automation (sensor technician, marine automation technician, automation engineer) [NEW] 98 %							
			Electromechanical engineering technician	YES	YES	NO										
			Electronics engineering technician	YES	YES	NO										
			Marine electronics technician	YES	YES	NO										
			Electronic equipment assembler	YES	YES	NO										
			Welder	YES	NO	YES										
			Boilermaker	YES	NO	YES										
			Pipe welder (pipe fitter)	YES	NO	YES										
			Sheet metal worker	YES	NO	YES										
			Surface treatment operator	YES	NO	YES										
			Abrasive blasting operator	YES	NO	YES										
Mobile crane operator	YES	NO	YES													

Production plant crane operator	YES	NO	YES
Shipwright	YES	NO	YES
Transport equipment painter	NO	NO	YES

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Shipbuilding)			Affected occupation and way they would be affected				Required skills and competences		Most effective training methods		Most effective educational methods		Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)		
2019	2025	2030		Re-training will be required	Dem and will increase	Demand will decrease									
<p>Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources</p>							By the year 2025	Engineering skills	By the year 2025	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer & by other providers	On the job training	57.0%	Alternative fuels (fuel cell engineer) [NEW]	93%	
			Marine engineering technician	YES	YES	NO	From year 2025 to 2030	Engineering skills & Transferable skills	From year 2025 to 2030	Vocational training (VET) by other providers	Educational programs with industry placements	62.0%	Energy management (planner, infrastructure engineer) [EXISTING]	95%	
			Marine engineering drafter	YES	NO	NO	From year 2030 and beyond	Transferable skills	From year 2030 and beyond		Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	67.0%			
			Marine engineer	YES	YES	NO	Most important Transferable skills: - Flexibility and adaptability - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy - Critical thinking and problem solving				From year 2030 and beyond	Webinars combined with training on the job	71.0%		
			Naval architect	YES	YES	NO					Life-long learning	88.0%			
			Vessel engine assembler	YES	YES	NO									

- Will become mainstream?: YES, Ranked 3rd with 83%
- Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked 3rd with 67%
- All genders would be equally affected
- Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected:
 - a) <2025: 35 years old and above
 - b) from 2025 to 2030: 35 years old to 55
 - c) >2030: equally all ages from 35 years old and above

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Shipbuilding)			Affected occupation and way they would be affected				Required skills and competences		Most effective training methods		Most effective educational methods		Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)			
2019	2025	2030														
<p>3D printing</p> <p>-Will become mainstream?: YES, Ranked last with 59% -Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked 5th with 52% -All genders would be equally affected - Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected: a) <2025: 35 years old and above b) from 2025 to 2030: 35 years old and above c) >2030: equally all ages from 25-35 and from 55 years old and above</p>							By the year 2025	Engineering skills	By the year 2025	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer	Educational programs with industry placements	55.0%	3D-printing (operator) [EXISTING]	93%		
							From year 2025 to 2030									Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)
							From year 2030 and beyond	Engineering skills & Transferable skills	From year 2025 to 2030	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer & by other providers	From year 2030 and beyond	Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)			58.0%	
												Webinars combined with training on the job			68.0%	
												Life-long learning			88.0%	

Most important Transferable skills:
 -Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
 -Flexibility and adaptability
 -Communication and collaboration

Table 25 Paradigm shifters in 3-time horizons and associated future scenarios on occupations (existing and new), skills, competences and training needs for the Offshore Renewable Energy sector (in the order of which will become mainstream first).

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Offshore Renewable Energy)			Affected occupation and way they would be affected	Required skills and competences	Most effective training methods	Most effective educational methods	Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)																																														
2019	2025	2030																																																			
<p>Smart grid and smart sensors</p> <p>-Will become mainstream?: YES, Ranked 1st with 82%</p> <p>-Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked 1st with 70%</p> <p>-All genders would be equally affected</p> <p>- Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected:</p> <p>a) <2025: from 35 years old and above</p> <p>b) from 2025 to 2030: mainly from 35 to 55 years old</p> <p>c) >2030: from 35 years old and above</p>			<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Re-training will be required</th> <th>Demand will increase</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Power distribution engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Electric power generation engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Maintenance and repair engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Power production plant operator</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Solar power plant operator</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Power distribution engineer	YES	YES	Electric power generation engineer	YES	YES	Maintenance and repair engineer	YES	YES	Power production plant operator	YES	YES	Solar power plant operator	YES	YES	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>By the year 2025</td> <td>Engineering skills & Transferable skills</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From year 2025 to 2030</td> <td>Engineering skills & Health & safety skills & Transferable skills</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From year 2030 and beyond</td> <td>Engineering skills & Transferable skills</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Most important Transferable skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy -Flexibility and adaptability -Communication and collaboration -Critical thinking and problem solving 	By the year 2025	Engineering skills & Transferable skills	From year 2025 to 2030	Engineering skills & Health & safety skills & Transferable skills	From year 2030 and beyond	Engineering skills & Transferable skills	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>By the year 2025</td> <td rowspan="3">Vocational training (VET) by other providers</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From year 2025 to 2030</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From year 2030 and beyond</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	By the year 2025	Vocational training (VET) by other providers	From year 2025 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI), Augmented reality, 3D applications)</td> <td>62 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Higher education new technology courses</td> <td>65 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Educational programs with industry placements</td> <td>65 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Webinars combined with training on the job</td> <td>68 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Life-long learning</td> <td>86 %</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI), Augmented reality, 3D applications)	62 %	Higher education new technology courses	65 %	Educational programs with industry placements	65 %	Webinars combined with training on the job	68 %	Life-long learning	86 %	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>Artificial Intelligence (AI) professional (NEW)</td> <td>89%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Remote controller (EXISTING)</td> <td>92%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sensors (developer, installer, technician) (NEW)</td> <td>95%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Big Data analyst (EXISTING)</td> <td>97%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Artificial Intelligence (AI) professional (NEW)	89%	Remote controller (EXISTING)	92%	Sensors (developer, installer, technician) (NEW)	95%	Big Data analyst (EXISTING)	97%
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Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Offshore Renewable Energy)		Affected occupation and way they would be affected		Required skills and competences	Most effective training methods	Most effective educational methods	Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)																																																																			
2019	2025	2030																																																																								
<p>Big data</p> <p>-Will become mainstream?: YES, Ranked second with 81%</p> <p>-Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked 2nd with 69%</p> <p>-All genders would be equally affected</p> <p>- Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected:</p> <p>a) <2025: from 35 years old and above</p> <p>b) from 2025 to 2030: 35 years old and above, but mainly ages from 35 to 45.</p> <p>c) >2030: ages from 55 years old and above</p>			<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td>Re-training will be required</td> <td>Demand will increase</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Renewable energy engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Energy systems engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Wind energy engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Power distribution engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Power production plant operator</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Electric power generation engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Maintenance and repair engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Wind turbine technician</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Solar energy engineer</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Solar energy technician</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Solar power plant operator</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hydropower technician</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Wave power technician</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tidal power technician</td> <td>YES</td> <td>YES</td> </tr> </table>		Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Renewable energy engineer	YES	YES	Energy systems engineer	YES	YES	Wind energy engineer	YES	YES	Power distribution engineer	YES	YES	Power production plant operator	YES	YES	Electric power generation engineer	YES	YES	Maintenance and repair engineer	YES	YES	Wind turbine technician	YES	YES	Solar energy engineer	YES	YES	Solar energy technician	YES	YES	Solar power plant operator	YES	YES	Hydropower technician	YES	YES	Wave power technician	YES	YES	Tidal power technician	YES	YES	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>By the year 2025</td> <td rowspan="3">Engineering skills & Transferable skills</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From year 2025 to 2030</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From year 2030 and beyond</td> </tr> </table> <p>Most important Transferable skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy -Flexibility and adaptability -Initiative and self-direction 	By the year 2025	Engineering skills & Transferable skills	From year 2025 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>By the year 2025</td> <td>Attend a higher education course</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From year 2025 to 2030</td> <td>Attend a higher education course & Vocational training (VET) by other providers</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From year 2030 and beyond</td> <td>Vocational training (VET) by other providers</td> </tr> </table>	By the year 2025	Attend a higher education course	From year 2025 to 2030	Attend a higher education course & Vocational training (VET) by other providers	From year 2030 and beyond	Vocational training (VET) by other providers	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Higher education new technology courses</td> <td>62 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)</td> <td>65 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Webinars combined with training on the job</td> <td>65 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)</td> <td>70 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Life-long learning</td> <td>89 %</td> </tr> </table>	Higher education new technology courses	62 %	Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	65 %	Webinars combined with training on the job	65 %	Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	70 %	Life-long learning	89 %	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Big Data systems (developer, engineer) (EXISTING)</td> <td>100%</td> </tr> </table>	Big Data systems (developer, engineer) (EXISTING)	100%
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Wave power technician	YES	YES																																																																								
Tidal power technician	YES	YES																																																																								
By the year 2025	Engineering skills & Transferable skills																																																																									
From year 2025 to 2030																																																																										
From year 2030 and beyond																																																																										
By the year 2025	Attend a higher education course																																																																									
From year 2025 to 2030	Attend a higher education course & Vocational training (VET) by other providers																																																																									
From year 2030 and beyond	Vocational training (VET) by other providers																																																																									
Higher education new technology courses	62 %																																																																									
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	65 %																																																																									
Webinars combined with training on the job	65 %																																																																									
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	70 %																																																																									
Life-long learning	89 %																																																																									
Big Data systems (developer, engineer) (EXISTING)	100%																																																																									

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Offshore Renewable Energy)		Affected occupation and way they would be affected			Required skills and competences	Most effective training methods	Most effective educational methods	Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)		
2019	2025	2030								
<p>Automation and advanced robotics</p>										
					By the year 2025	Engineering skills	Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI), Augmented reality, 3D applications) 58%	Sustainability engineer (EXISTING)	76%	
					From year 2025 to 2030	Engineering skills		Mechatronics technician (EXISTING)	79%	
						From year 2030 and beyond	Engineering skills & Health & safety skills & Transferable skills	Higher education new technology courses 63% Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility) 71% Webinars combined with training on the job 71% Life-long learning 92%	Predictive maintenance analyst (EXISTING)	84%
									Big Data manager (EXISTING)	92%
									Virtual Reality (VR) designer (EXISTING)	92%
									Cyber security expert (NEW)	92%
									Drone and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) pilot-operator (EXISTING)	95%
									Artificial Intelligence (AI) professional (NEW)	95%
									Robotics (constructor, programmer, operator) (NEW)	97%
									Autonomous system operator (NEW)	97%

-Will become mainstream?: YES, Ranked 3rd with 79%
 -Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked 3rd with 67%
 -All genders would be equally affected
 -Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected:
 a) <2025: 55 years old and above
 b) from 2025 to 2030: Mainly 35-45 years old, but also ages from 45 years old and above
 c) >2030: from 55 years old and above

Most important Transferable skills:
 -Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
 -Flexibility and adaptability
 -Communication and collaboration

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Offshore Renewable Energy)			Affected occupation and way they would be affected	Required skills and competences	Most effective training methods	Most effective educational methods	Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)
2019	2025	2030					

Energy storage

-Will become mainstream?
: YES, Ranked 2nd with 81%
-Will affect the job situation in Europe?:
YES, Ranked 4th with 58%
-All genders would be equally affected
- Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected:
a) <2025: all ages ≥ 35 years old
b) from 2025 to 2030: mainly ages from 35 to 55 years old
c) >2030: ages 35-45 and ages ≥ 55

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase
Power production plant operator	YES	YES
Solar power plant operator	YES	YES
Power distribution engineer	YES	YES
Electric power generation engineer	YES	YES
Maintenance and repair engineer	YES	YES

By the year 2025	Engineering skills & Transferable skills
From year 2025 to 2030	
From year 2030 and beyond	

Most important Transferable skills:
-Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
-Flexibility and adaptability
-Communication and collaboration together with Creative thinking and innovation

By the year 2025	Attend a higher education course & Vocational training (VET) by the current employer & Vocational training (VET) by other providers
From year 2025 to 2030	Vocational training (VET) by other providers
From year 2030 and beyond	Vocational training (VET) by other providers

Educational programs with industry placements	57 %
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	59 %
Webinars combined with training on the job	68 %
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI), Augmented reality, 3D applications)	68 %
Life-long learning	86 %

Grid Insulation and Construction professional (EXISTING)	78%
Energy storage specialist (NEW)	95%

Timeline of Paradigm shifters becoming mainstream (Offshore Renewable Energy)			Affected occupation and way they would be affected	Required skills and competences	Most effective training methods	Most effective educational methods	Expected emerging occupations (New and existing that gain relevance)
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2019 2025 2030

3D printing

-Will become mainstream?: YES, Ranked last (5th) with 59%
 -Will affect the job situation in Europe?: YES, Ranked last (5th) with 50%
 -All genders would be equally affected
 - Ages of the workforce (adversely) affected:
 a) <2025: ages 35-45 years old and from 55 and above
 b) from 2025 to 2030: ages from 25 years old and above
 c) >2030: ages from 55 years old and above

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease
Welder	YES	NO	YES
Wave power technician	YES	YES	NO
Electromechanical equipment assembler	YES	YES	NO
Wind turbine technician	YES	YES	NO
Tidal power technician	YES	YES	NO
Solar energy technician	YES	YES	NO
Hydropower technician	YES	YES	NO
Electromechanical engineering technician	YES	YES	NO
Electronic equipment assembler	YES	YES	NO
Printed circuit board assembler	YES	YES	NO

By the year 2025	Engineering skills & Transferable skills
From year 2025 to 2030	
From year 2030 and beyond	

Most important Transferable skills:
 -Information and Technologies (ICT) Literacy Communication
 -Flexibility and adaptability
 -Critical thinking and problem solving
 -Creative thinking and innovation

By the year 2025	Vocational training (VET) by the current employer & by other providers
From year 2025 to 2030	
From year 2030 and beyond	

Higher education new technology courses	54%
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	54%
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	59%
Webinars combined with training on the job	59%
Life-long learning	84%

3D printer maintenance worker (NEW)	84%
Designer of parts for 3D printing (NEW)	92%
3D printing (technician, engineer, expert) (NEW)	97%

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11 Delphi Questionnaires - Annex A

MATES DELPHI QUESTIONNAIRE - Round 1

MARITIME ALLIANCE FOR FOSTERING THE EUROPEAN BLUE ECONOMY THROUGH A MARINE TECHNOLOGY SKILLING STRATEGY (MATES)

T2.3 ANALYSIS OF TRENDS AND PARADIGM SHIFTERS

Introduction

Dear respondent,

As part of "T2.3 Analysis of Trends and Paradigm Shifters" a first round questionnaire has been designed based on the Delphi methodology in order to congregate experts' opinions through a series of iterative questionnaires with a goal of achieving a group consensus on the relevant trends and paradigm shifters. The estimated completion time of the questionnaire is about 40 minutes.

The questionnaire is addressing two specific groups of experts in the sectors of *Shipbuilding* and *Offshore Renewable energies* and it is split in two (2) main sections. The first main section is to capture the respondents personal & company details and the second focuses on the paradigm shifters identified as most significant for the future.

The selected paradigm shifters for each sector are as follows:

A. Shipbuilding

1. Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics
2. Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources
3. Digitalization
4. 3D Printing
5. Green retrofitting
6. Drones

B. Offshore Renewable Energies

1. Automation & Advanced robotics
2. 3D Printing
3. Smart grid & Smart sensors
4. Big data
5. Energy storage

For each selected paradigm shifter, a relevant Delphi template consisting of 12 questions has been designed in order to address issues such as:

- How will the overall Maritime Technologies sector be affected (in terms of emerging, declining and disappearing jobs)?
- How existing jobs will be affected (need for reskilling, upgrading, ...)?
- What new jobs / responsibilities / tasks will emerge?
- What jobs might disappear (and hence the need to educate/train people for them) and whether the affected people have transferable skills for other types of jobs?
- Which market types (genders, age, abilities, education level, competences and skills) will be needed and which will be available at the then workforce?
- How can training and retraining of employees help in preventing job losses?

A very useful companion for the completion of this questionnaire is the "Baseline Report on Present Skills Gaps in Shipbuilding and Offshore Renewables Value Chains" (e-mailed to you on 08 March 2019), which presents a critical review and analysis of the existing needs for education, training and skills in the sectors of shipbuilding and offshore renewables in Europe.

Once MATES receives all the responses from round one, the results will be analysed and you may be contacted again with a second round of questions in order to achieve a clear group consensus on the relevant trends and paradigm shifters.

We are looking forward to receiving your valuable input and we thank you very much in advance.

The MATES Project Team

Page 1 - Personal info and Company info

PERSONAL INFORMATION

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

1. NAME, SURNAME & GENDER

	Name	Surname	Gender	Prefer to be anonymous
Respondent Details	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	Select one ▼	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 2. EMAIL

* 3. AGE RANGE

- up to 25 years old
- between 25 and 35
- between 35 and 45
- between 45 and 55
- above 55 years old

* 4. CURRENT POSITION WITHIN ORGANISATION

- Researcher (University)
- Researcher (industry/commercial sector)
- Director/Manager/Head of department (research / (higher) education)
- Director/Manager/Head of department (industry/commercial sector)
- University Faculty member (i.e. professors of various ranks, lecturer)
- Educator (i.e. trainer, teacher etc.)
- Other, please specify

* 5. Years of Experience

- up to 5
- between 5 and up to 10
- between 10 and up to 15
- between 15 and up to 20
- over 20

* 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE

- Shipbuilding
- Shipbuilding & Offshore Renewable energies
- Offshore Renewable energies

COMPANY INFORMATION

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 7. NAME OF ORGANISATION

* 8. ORGANISATION URL

*** 9. ORGANISATION SIZE**

- Micro (fewer than 10 persons employed)
- Small (10 to 49 persons employed)
- Medium (50 to 249 persons employed)
- Large (250 or more persons employed)

*** 10. ORGANISATION'S COUNTRY**

[Please choose only ONE. If your organisation operates in more than one country please select the one which represents the largest proportion of staff employment.]

- | | |
|---|--------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Austria | <input type="radio"/> Belgium |
| <input type="radio"/> Bulgaria | <input type="radio"/> Croatia |
| <input type="radio"/> Cyprus | <input type="radio"/> Czech Republic |
| <input type="radio"/> Denmark | <input type="radio"/> Estonia |
| <input type="radio"/> Finland | <input type="radio"/> France |
| <input type="radio"/> Germany | <input type="radio"/> Greece |
| <input type="radio"/> Hungary | <input type="radio"/> Ireland |
| <input type="radio"/> Italy | <input type="radio"/> Latvia |
| <input type="radio"/> Lithuania | <input type="radio"/> Luxembourg |
| <input type="radio"/> Malta | <input type="radio"/> Netherlands |
| <input type="radio"/> Poland | <input type="radio"/> Portugal |
| <input type="radio"/> Romania | <input type="radio"/> Slovakia |
| <input type="radio"/> Slovenia | <input type="radio"/> Spain |
| <input type="radio"/> Sweden | <input type="radio"/> United Kingdom |
| <input type="radio"/> Other, please specify | |

*** 11. SEA BASIN IN WHICH THE MAIN ACTIVITY OF THE ORGANISATION TAKES PLACE**

[Please choose only ONE. If your organisation operates in more than one sea basin please select the one which represents the largest proportion of staff employment.]

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Adriatic and Ionian Seas | <input type="radio"/> Atlantic Ocean |
| <input type="radio"/> Arctic Ocean | <input type="radio"/> Baltic Sea |
| <input type="radio"/> Black Sea | <input type="radio"/> Mediterranean Sea |
| <input type="radio"/> North Sea | <input type="radio"/> Outermost Regions |
| <input type="radio"/> Other, please specify | |

*** 12. TYPE OF ORGANISATION**

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Enterprise | <input type="radio"/> Industry Association |
| <input type="radio"/> Other Organisation delivering training | <input type="radio"/> Cluster |
| <input type="radio"/> Research Organisation | <input type="radio"/> Administration |
| <input type="radio"/> Other, please specify | |

Page 2 - ENTERPRISE, INDUSTRY ASSOCIATION and CLUSTER

 Show page if
 12. TYPE OF ORGANISATION
 is Enterprise
 or

12. TYPE OF ORGANISATION
is *Industry Association*
or
12. TYPE OF ORGANISATION
is *Cluster*

SECTION APPLICABLE ONLY TO ORGANISATION TYPES: ENTERPRISE, INDUSTRY ASSOCIATION and CLUSTER
[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 13. HOW EASY/DIFFICULT IT IS TO FIND EMPLOYEES WITH THE REQUIRED SKILLS IN YOUR SECTOR?

- Very difficult
- Neutral
- Very easy
- Other, please specify
- Difficult
- Easy
- I do not know

* 14. DO YOU THINK THAT THE CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS IN YOUR COUNTRY CAN PROVIDE THE REQUIRED SKILLS TO THE WORKFORCE ?

- Strongly disagree
- Neutral
- Strongly agree
- Other, please specify
- Disagree
- Agree
- I do not know

* 15. WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING YOU THINK ARE CURRENT SKILLS' GAPS IN YOUR SECTOR?

- Creative thinking and Innovation
- Communication and collaboration
- Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
- Initiative and self-direction
- Leadership and responsibility
- I do not know
- Critical thinking and problem solving
- Knowledge management and transfer
- Flexibility and adaptability
- Productivity and accountability
- All the above
- Other, please specify

Page 3 - Shipping -Automation 0

* **Don't show page** if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is *Offshore Renewable energies*

1) VESSEL AUTOMATION, VESSEL AUTONOMY AND ADVANCED ROBOTICS (E.G. WELDING AND BLASTING ROBOTS)
SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 16. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all likely Extremely likely

* 17. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all likely Extremely likely

• Go to page 6 - Shipping-ALTERNATIVE FUELS 0 if
 16. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?
 less than 4
 and
 17. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?
 less than 4

Page 4 - Shipping -Automation 1

• Don't show page if
 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 is Offshore Renewable energies

1) VESSEL AUTOMATION, VESSEL AUTONOMY AND ADVANCED ROBOTICS (E.G. WELDING AND BLASTING ROBOTS)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 18. IN WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?

By the year 2025 From year 2025 to 2030
 From year 2030 and beyond

* 19. HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?

	Slightly Affected	Affected	Reshaped	Fully reshaped	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

• Go to page 6 - Shipping-ALTERNATIVE FUELS 0 if
 19.1. By the year 2025
 is N/A
 and
 19.2. From year 2025 to 2030
 is N/A
 and
 19.3. From year 2030 and beyond
 is N/A

Page 5 - Shipping-Automation 2

🚫 Don't show page if

6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

**1) VESSEL AUTOMATION, VESSEL AUTONOMY AND ADVANCED ROBOTICS
(E.G. WELDING AND BLASTING ROBOTS)**

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 20. WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2025	From year 2025 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Naval architect	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electronics engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Welder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Shipwright	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Boilermaker	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Pipe welder (pipe fitter)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sheet metal worker	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine electronics technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electronic equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Surface treatment operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Transport equipment painter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Abrasive blasting operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Mobile crane operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Production plant crane operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 21. WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

By the year From year From year

N/A

	2025	2025 to 2030	2030 and beyond
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 22. WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 25 years old	between 25 and 35	between 36 and 45	between 46 and 65	above 65 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>				

* 23. DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 24. WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 25. WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	Engineering skills (i.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	Health & safety skills (i.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Transferable skills (i.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy, initiative and self-direction etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 26. HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE Institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 27. WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E. LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 6 - Shipping-ALTERNATIVE FUELS 0

* Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE

is Offshore Renewable energies

2) EXPLOITATION OF ALTERNATIVE FUELS AND RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES (E.G. LNG, ELECTRIFICATION, FLETTNER ROTORS, ETC.)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 28. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all likely	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely likely										

* 29. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all likely	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely likely										

- Go to page 9 - Shipping-Digitalization 0 if
 - 28. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM? less than 4
 - and
 - 29. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE? less than 4

Page 7 - Shipping-ALTERNATIVE FUELS 1

⚠ Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

2) EXPLOITATION OF ALTERNATIVE FUELS AND RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES (E.G. LNG, ELECTRIFICATION, FLETTNER ROTORS, ETC.)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 30. IN WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?

- By the year 2025
- From year 2025 to 2030
- From year 2030 and beyond

* 31. HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?

	Slightly Affected	Affected	Reshaped	Fully reshaped	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

- Go to page 9 - Shipping-Digitalization 0 if
 - 31.1. By the year 2025
is N/A
 - and
 - 31.2. From year 2025 to 2030
is N/A
 - and
 - 31.3. From year 2030 and beyond
is N/A
- Else go to page 8 - Shipping-ALTERNATIVE FUELS 2

Page 8 - Shipping-ALTERNATIVE FUELS 2

🚫 **Don't show page** if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

2) EXPLOITATION OF ALTERNATIVE FUELS AND RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES (E.G. LNG, ELECTRIFICATION, FLETTNER ROTORS, ETC.)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 32.WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Naval architect	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineering drafter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vessel engine assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Boat rigger	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 33.WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** 34. WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?**
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 25 years old	between 25 and 36	between 36 and 46	between 46 and 66	above 66 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

*** 35. DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?**

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** 36. WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** 37. WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

Engineering skills (I.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	Health & safety skills (I.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Transferable skills (I.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy, initiative and	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	self-direction etc.)			
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 38. HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE Institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 39. WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E. LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 9 - Shipping-Digitalization 0

⚠️ Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

3) DIGITALIZATION (E.G. BIG DATA ANALYTICS, INTERNET OF THINGS APPLICATIONS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, SMART SENSORS, ETC.)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 40. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

Not at all likely 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Extremely likely

* 41. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?

Not at all likely 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Extremely likely

- Go to page 12 - Shipping-3D Printing 0 if
40. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?
less than 4
and
41. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?
less than 4

Page 10 - Shipping-Digitalization 1

Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

3) DIGITALIZATION (E.G. BIG DATA ANALYTICS, INTERNET OF THINGS APPLICATIONS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, SMART SENSORS, ETC.)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 42. IN WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?

By the year 2025 From year 2025 to 2030
 From year 2030 and beyond

* 43. HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?

	Slightly Affected	Affected	Reshaped	Fully reshaped	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

- Go to page 12 - Shipping-3D Printing 0 if
43.1. By the year 2025
is N/A
and
43.2. From year 2025 to 2030
is N/A
and
43.3. From year 2030 and beyond

- is N/A
- Else go to page 11 - Shipping-Digitalization 2

Page 11 - Shipping-Digitalization 2

🚫 Don't show page if
 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 is Offshore Renewable energies

3) DIGITALIZATION (E.G. BIG DATA ANALYTICS, INTERNET OF THINGS APPLICATIONS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, SMART SENSORS, ETC.)
 SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 44. WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Naval architect	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electronics engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineering drafter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical drafter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineering drafter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine electronics technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electronic equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 45. WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 46. WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?**
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 26 years old	between 26 and 35	between 36 and 45	between 46 and 65	above 65 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>				

*** 47. DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?**

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 48. WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 49. WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

Engineering skills (i.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding	Health & safety skills (i.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety	Transferable skills (i.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy,	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	the physics of a task etc.)	equipment etc.)	Initiative and self-direction etc.)	
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 50.HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 51.WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Page 12 - Shipping-3D Printing 0

⚠ Don't show page if
 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 is Offshore Renewable energies

4) 3D PRINTING (OF VESSEL PARTS AND BLOCKS, TOOLS AND MACHINE PARTS, ETC.)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 52. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all likely Extremely likely

* 53. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all likely Extremely likely

- Go to page 15 - Shipping-Green retrofitting 0 if
 - 52. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM? less than 4
 - and
 - 53. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE? less than 4

Page 13 - Shipping-3D Printing 1

- Don't show page if
 - 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE is Offshore Renewable energies

4) 3D PRINTING (OF VESSEL PARTS AND BLOCKS, TOOLS AND MACHINE PARTS, ETC.)
 SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 54. IN WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?

By the year 2025
 From year 2025 to 2030
 From year 2030 and beyond

* 55. HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?

	Slightly Affected	Affected	Reshaped	Fully reshaped	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

- Go to page 15 - Shipping-Green retrofitting 0 if
 - 55.1. By the year 2025 is N/A
 - and
 - 55.2. From year 2025 to 2030 is N/A
 - and

55.3. From year 2030 and beyond
is N/A
• Else go to page 14 - Shipping-3D Printing 2

Page 14 - Shipping-3D Printing 2

⚠ Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

4) 3D PRINTING (OF VESSEL PARTS AND BLOCKS, TOOLS AND MACHINE PARTS, ETC.)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 56. WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Welder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Shipwright	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Boilermaker	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Pipe welder (pipe fitter)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vessel engine assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Boat rigger	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Computer numerical control (CNC) machine operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 57. WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** 58. WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?**
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 25 years old	between 25 and 36	between 36 and 46	between 46 and 56	above 56 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

*** 59. DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?**

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** 60. WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** 61. WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

	Engineering skills (I.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	Health & safety skills (I.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Transferable skills (I.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, information and communication Technologies (ICT) literacy, Initiative and self-direction etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 62. HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE Institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 63. WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E. LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 15 - Shipping-Green retrofitting 0

⚠ Don't show page if
 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 is Offshore Renewable energies

5) GREEN RETROFITTING (E.G. SCRUBBER INSTALLATION, BALLAST WATER TREATMENT RETROFITS)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 64. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Page 17 - Shipping-Green retrofitting 2

* Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

5) GREEN RETROFITTING (E.G. SCRUBBER INSTALLATION, BALLAST WATER TREATMENT RETROFITS)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 68.WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Naval architect	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Welding inspector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Welder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Shipwright	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Boat rigger	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 69.WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 70. WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 26 years old	between 26 and 36	between 36 and 46	between 46 and 56	above 56 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

* 71. DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 72. WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 73. WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	Engineering skills (I.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	Health & safety skills (I.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Transferable skills (I.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy, Initiative and self-direction etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 74. HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE Institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 75. WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E. LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Page 18 - Shipping-Drones 0

⚠ Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

6) DRONES (FOR VESSEL INSPECTIONS)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 76. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

Not at all likely 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Extremely likely

* 77. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?

Not at all likely 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Extremely likely

- Go to thank-you page if
 - 76. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?
 - less than 4
 - and
 - 77. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?
 - less than 4
 - and
 - 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 - is Shipbuilding
- Go to page 21 - Offshore-Automation 0 if
 - 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 - is Shipbuilding & Offshore Renewable energies

Page 19 - Shipping-Drones 1

- **Don't show page** if
 - 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 - is Offshore Renewable energies

6) DRONES (FOR VESSEL INSPECTIONS)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 78. IN WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?

- By the year 2025
- From year 2025 to 2030
- From year 2030 and beyond

* 79. HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?

	Slightly Affected	Affected	Reshaped	Fully reshaped	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

- Go to thank-you page if
 - 79.1. By the year 2025
 - is N/A
 - and
 - 79.2. From year 2025 to 2030
 - is N/A
 - and
 - 79.3. From year 2030 and beyond
 - is N/A
 - and
 - 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 - is Shipbuilding
- Go to page 21 - Offshore-Automation 0 if
 - 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 - is Shipbuilding & Offshore Renewable energies
- Else go to page 20 - Shipping-Drones 2

Page 20 - Shipping-Drones 2

* Don't show page if

6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

6) DRONES (FOR VESSEL INSPECTIONS)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 80. WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Welding inspector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine upholsterer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vessel assembly supervisor	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vessel assembly inspector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine surveyor	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 81. WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 82. WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?

["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

up to 26 years old between 26 and 35 between 36 and 45 between 46 and 55 above 55 years old

By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

* 83.DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 84.WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 85.WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	Engineering skills (i.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	Health & safety skills (i.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Transferable skills (i.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, information and communication technologies (ICT) literacy, initiative and self-direction etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 86.HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

Attend a higher education course (i.e. ...)	Via vocational education and training (VET)	Via vocational education and training (VET)	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	at a university)	offered by the current employer	offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE Institutes etc.)	
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 87. WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- Go to page 21 - Offshore-Automation 0 if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding & Offshore Renewable energies
- Else go to thank-you page

Page 21 - Offshore-Automation 0

- Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

1) AUTOMATION & ADVANCED ROBOTICS (SUCH AS REMOTELY OPERATED VEHICLES, DRONES, ETC. USED IN SURVEYS, INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS TRANSFER, INSPECTIONS, MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR)
SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 88. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all likely Extremely likely

* 89. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

1) AUTOMATION & ADVANCED ROBOTICS (SUCH AS REMOTELY OPERATED VEHICLES, DRONES, ETC. USED IN SURVEYS, INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS TRANSFER, INSPECTIONS, MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 92.WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Maintenance and repair engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Welder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wind turbine technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Solar energy technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Hydropower technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tidal power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wave power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electronic equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Printed circuit board assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cable installer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Construction commercial diver	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 93.WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Productivity and accountability				
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 94. WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 26 years old	between 26 and 36	between 36 and 46	between 46 and 66	above 66 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>				

* 95. DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 96. WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 97. WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	Engineering skills (I.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	Health & safety skills (I.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Transferable skills (I.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy, Initiative and self-direction etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 98.HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE Institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 99.WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 24 - Offshore-3D Printing 0

* Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

2) 3D PRINTING (FOR MASSIVE PRODUCTION OF INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS USED IN CONSTRUCTION AND INSTALLATION, AS WELL AS IN REPAIR)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 10QWILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

Not at all likely	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely likely										
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* 10 WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all likely Extremely likely

- Go to page 27 - Offshore-Smart grid 0 if
 - 100. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM? less than 4
 - and
 - 101. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?... less than 4

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- Don't show page if
 - 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE is Shipbuilding

2) 3D PRINTING (FOR MASSIVE PRODUCTION OF INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS USED IN CONSTRUCTION AND INSTALLATION, AS WELL AS IN REPAIR)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 102N WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?

- By the year 2025
- From year 2025 to 2030
- From year 2030 and beyond

* 103 HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?

	Slightly Affected	Affected	Reshaped	Fully reshaped	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

- Go to page 27 - Offshore-Smart grid 0 if
 - 103.1. By the year 2025 is N/A
 - and
 - 103.2. From year 2025 to 2030 is N/A
 - and
 - 103.3. From year 2030 and beyond is N/A

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❗ Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

2) 3D PRINTING (FOR MASSIVE PRODUCTION OF INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS USED IN CONSTRUCTION AND INSTALLATION, AS WELL AS IN REPAIR)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 104 WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Welder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wind turbine technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar energy technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hydropower technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tidal power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wave power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electronic equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Printed circuit board assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 105 WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 108 WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?**
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 26 years old	between 26 and 36	between 36 and 46	between 46 and 66	above 66 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>				

*** 109 DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?**

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 108 WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 109 WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

	Engineering skills (I.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	Health & safety skills (I.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Transferable skills (I.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy, Initiative and self-direction etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 110 HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE Institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 111 WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E. LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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* Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

3) SMART GRID & SMART SENSORS (FOR REMOTE OPERATION OF THE OFFSHORE RENEWABLES FARMS, AUTO-INSPECTIONS OF THE INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS, AUTO-REPAIR OF ELECTROMECHANICAL ASPECTS OF THE INFRASTRUCTURES AND EFFICIENT POWER DISTRIBUTION TO THE ELECTRICITY GRID)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 112 WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all likely Extremely likely

* 113 WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all likely Extremely likely

- Go to page 30 - Offshore-Big data 0 if
 - 112. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM? less than 4
 - and
 - 113. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?... less than 4

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- Don't show page if
 - 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE is Shipbuilding

3) SMART GRID & SMART SENSORS (FOR REMOTE OPERATION OF THE OFFSHORE RENEWABLES FARMS, AUTO-INSPECTIONS OF THE INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS, AUTO-REPAIR OF ELECTROMECHANICAL ASPECTS OF THE INFRASTRUCTURES AND EFFICIENT POWER DISTRIBUTION TO THE ELECTRICITY GRID)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 114N WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?

- By the year 2025
- From year 2025 to 2030
- From year 2030 and beyond

* 115 HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?

	Slightly Affected	Affected	Reshaped	Fully reshaped	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

- Go to page 30 - Offshore-Big data 0 if
 - 115.1. By the year 2025 is N/A
 - and
 - 115.2. From year 2025 to 2030 is N/A

and
115.3. From year 2030 and beyond
is N/A

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⚠ Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

3) SMART GRID & SMART SENSORS (FOR REMOTE OPERATION OF THE OFFSHORE RENEWABLES FARMS, AUTO-INSPECTIONS OF THE INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS, AUTO-REPAIR OF ELECTROMECHANICAL ASPECTS OF THE INFRASTRUCTURES AND EFFICIENT POWER DISTRIBUTION TO THE ELECTRICITY GRID)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 116WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2025	From year 2025 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Power distribution engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electric power generation engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maintenance and repair engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Power production plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar power plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 117WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2025	From year 2025 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 118 WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?**
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 25 years old	between 26 and 36	between 36 and 46	between 46 and 66	above 66 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>				

*** 119 DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?**

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 120 WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 121 WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

	Engineering skills (I.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	Health & safety skills (I.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Transferable skills (I.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy, Initiative and self-direction etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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* 12 HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 13 WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E. LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Page 30 - Offshore-Big data 0

⚠ Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

4) BIG DATA (FOR RECORDING AND MANAGING REAL-TIME, OF LARGE AMOUNT DATA, WHICH CAN CONTRIBUTE TO ENERGY SYSTEMS EFFICIENCY OPTIMIZATION, AS WELL AS OPERATIONS' OPTIMIZATION AND PREDICTIONS FOR MAINTENANCE)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 14 WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

Not at all likely	<input type="radio"/>	0	<input type="radio"/>	1	<input type="radio"/>	2	<input type="radio"/>	3	<input type="radio"/>	4	<input type="radio"/>	5	<input type="radio"/>	6	<input type="radio"/>	7	<input type="radio"/>	8	<input type="radio"/>	9	<input type="radio"/>	10	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely likely
-------------------	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	---	-----------------------	----	-----------------------	------------------

Page 32 - Offshore-Big data 2

⚠ Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

4) BIG DATA (FOR RECORDING AND MANAGING REAL-TIME, OF LARGE AMOUNT DATA, WHICH CAN CONTRIBUTE TO ENERGY SYSTEMS EFFICIENCY OPTIMIZATION, AS WELL AS OPERATIONS' OPTIMIZATION AND PREDICTIONS FOR MAINTENANCE)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 129 WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Renewable energy engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Energy systems engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wind energy engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar energy engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Power distribution engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electric power generation engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maintenance and repair engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wind turbine technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar energy technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hydropower technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tidal power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wave power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Power production plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar power plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 129 WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 130WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?**
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 25 years old	between 26 and 36	between 36 and 46	between 46 and 66	above 66 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>				

*** 131DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?**

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 132WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*** 133WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?**

Engineering skills (I.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with	Health & safety skills (I.e. Work at heights, Work in	Transferable skills (I.e. Critical thinking and problem solving,	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy, initiative and self-direction etc.)	
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 13.4 HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE Institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 13.5 WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E. LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Page 33 - Offshore-Energy storage 0

⚠ Don't show page if
6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

5) ENERGY STORAGE (NEW BATTERY TECHNOLOGY, ETC.)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 138 WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM?

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all likely	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely likely										

* 137 WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all likely	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely likely										

- Go to thank-you page if
 - 136. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER BECOME MAINSTREAM? less than 4
 - and
 - 137. WILL THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER AFFECT (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION IN EUROPE?... less than 4

Page 34 - Offshore-Energy storage 1

- Don't show page if
 - 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE is Shipbuilding

5) ENERGY STORAGE (NEW BATTERY TECHNOLOGY, ETC.)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 138N WHICH TIME HORIZON THIS PARADIGM SHIFTER IS LIKELY TO BECOME MAINSTREAM?

- By the year 2025
- From year 2025 to 2030
- From year 2030 and beyond

* 139 HOW WOULD THE CURRENT JOB SITUATION BE (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER?

	Slightly Affected	Affected	Reshaped	Fully reshaped	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

- Go to thank-you page if
 - 139.1. By the year 2025 is N/A
 - and
 - 139.2. From year 2025 to 2030

is N/A
 and
 139.3. From year 2030 and beyond
 is N/A
 • Else go to page 35 - Offshore-Energy storage 2

Page 35 - Offshore-Energy storage 2

⚠️ **Don't show page if**
 6. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 is Shipbuilding

5) ENERGY STORAGE (NEW BATTERY TECHNOLOGY, ETC.)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 14 WHAT EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WILL BE MOST (ADVERSELY OR FAVOURABLY) AFFECTED ?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Power distribution engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electric power generation engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maintenance and repair engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Power production plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar power plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 14 WHAT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS SHOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR ETC?

	By the year 2026	From year 2026 to 2030	From year 2030 and beyond	N/A
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 142 WHAT AGES OF THE WORKFORCE WOULD BE MOST (ADVERSELY) AFFECTED?
 ["Ages": The ages of the workforce during the deployment of the current research]

	up to 25 years old	between 26 and 36	between 36 and 46	between 46 and 56	above 56 years old
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>				
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>				

* 143 DO YOU CONSIDER THAT THE IMPACT WILL BE DIFFERENT DEPENDING ON THE GENDER OF THE WORKFORCE (I.E. WHO WILL BE MORE AFFECTED)?

	Only male	Only female	Male more than female or other	Female more than male or other	Equally affected
By the year 2025	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 144 WHAT ARE THE NEW JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	New jobs that will emerge (Free text answer)	I do not know
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 145 WHAT WOULD BE THE REQUIRED SKILLS AND COMPETENCES FOR THE JOBS THAT WILL EMERGE?

	Engineering skills (I.e. CAD (Computer Aided Design), Working with tools and technology, Understanding the physics of a task etc.)	Health & safety skills (I.e. Work at heights, Work in confined spaces, Use of safety equipment etc.)	Transferable skills (I.e. Critical thinking and problem solving, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy, Initiative and self-direction etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** 14 HOW WOULD THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE BE RETRAINED IN ORDER TO CATCH UP WITH THE NEW DEVELOPMENT AND REMAIN EMPLOYABLE IN THE SAME SECTOR?**

	Attend a higher education course (i.e. at a university)	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by the current employer	Via vocational education and training (VET) offered by other providers (i.e. Universities, TAFE Institutes etc.)	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other, please specify	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*** 14 WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL METHODS THAT WOULD PROVIDE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY (I.E LOW COST, LESS TRAINING TIME, CURRENTLY OR NOT CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROGRAMS ETC.)?**

	Please specify	N/A
By the year 2025	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2025 to 2030	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From year 2030 and beyond	<input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Your responses have been registered!

Thank you for taking the time to complete the survey, your input is valuable to us. Obtaining information from organisations such as yours will provide the project team with the necessary information required in order to ensure the highest level of quality for the MATES deliverables.

Once MATES receives all the responses from round one, the results will be analysed and you may be contacted again with a second round of questions in order to achieve a clear group consensus on the relevant trends and paradigm shifters.

We really appreciate your efforts and we are confident that the information provided will be effectively used for the MATES project.

Many thanks

The MATES Project Team

12 Delphi Questionnaires - Annex B

MATES DELPHI QUESTIONNAIRE - Round 2

MARITIME ALLIANCE FOR FOSTERING THE EUROPEAN BLUE ECONOMY THROUGH A MARINE TECHNOLOGY SKILLING STRATEGY (MATES)

T2.3 ANALYSIS OF TRENDS AND PARADIGM SHIFTERS

Introduction

Dear respondent,

Following the first successful round, a second questionnaire has been designed based on the Delphi methodology in order to congregate your opinions on the relevant trends and paradigm shifters, which is part of "T2.3 Analysis of Trends and Paradigm Shifters" task.

The estimated completion time of this questionnaire is about 10 minutes, which is considerably less than the first round.

The 1st Delphi round revealed many interesting points ([click here to open](#)) which could be further investigated and help in drawing useful conclusions on the future scenarios related to skills and competences, as well as gaps in the current and foreseen occupational profiles at the short, mid and long-term.

This questionnaire is addressing the same two groups of experts in the sectors of *Shipbuilding* and *Offshore Renewable Energies* and it is split in two (2) main sections:

-The first is to capture the respondents personal & company details and

-The second focuses on the paradigm shifters identified as most significant for the future.

The opinions of the respondents from the 1st Delphi round supported that all of the paradigm shifters dealt with so far, for each sector, would become mainstream by the year 2030. So, the same paradigm shifters will be considered herein:

A. Shipbuilding

1. Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics
2. Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources
3. Digitalization
4. 3D Printing
5. Green retrofitting
6. Drones

B. Offshore Renewable Energies

1. Automation & Advanced robotics
2. 3D Printing
3. Smart grid & Smart sensors
4. Big data
5. Energy storage

For each selected paradigm shifter, a relevant Delphi template consisting of 4 questions has been designed in order to address issues mainly related to:

- What new jobs / responsibilities / tasks will emerge?
- What jobs might disappear (and hence the need to educate/train people for them) and whether the affected people have transferable skills for other types of jobs?
- How can training and retraining of employees help in preventing job losses?

A very useful companion for the completion of this questionnaire is the updated version of the "Baseline Report on Present Skills Gaps in Shipbuilding and Offshore Renewable Value Chains" ([click here to open](#)), which presents a critical review and analysis of the existing needs for education, training and skills in the sectors of shipbuilding and offshore renewable energy in Europe.

We are looking forward to receiving your valuable input and we thank you very much in advance.

The MATES Project Team

Page 1 - Personal info and Company info

PERSONAL INFORMATION
[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

1. NAME, SURNAME & GENDER

	Name	Surname	Gender	Prefer to be anonymous
Respondent Details			Select one ▼	<input type="radio"/>

*** 2. EMAIL**

*** 3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE**

- Shipbuilding
- Shipbuilding & Offshore Renewable energies
- Offshore Renewable energies

COMPANY INFORMATION
[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

*** 4. ORGANISATION'S COUNTRY**

[Please choose only ONE. If your organisation operates in more than one country please select the one which represents the largest proportion of staff employment.]

- Austria
- Bulgaria
- Cyprus
- Denmark
- Finland
- Germany
- Hungary
- Italy
- Lithuania
- Malta
- Poland
- Romania
- Slovenia
- Sweden
- Other, please specify
- Belgium
- Croatia
- Czech Republic
- Estonia
- France
- Greece
- Ireland
- Latvia
- Luxembourg
- Netherlands
- Portugal
- Slovakia
- Spain
- United Kingdom

*** 5. TYPE OF ORGANISATION**

- Enterprise
- Other Organisation delivering training
- Research Organisation
- Industry Association
- Cluster
- Administration

Page 2 - OVERVIEW OF SHIPBUILDING 1

🚫 Don't show page if

3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is *Offshore Renewable energies*

1st Delphi Round Overview (Shipbuilding)

From the 1st Delphi round, the majority of the respondents supported that all of the paradigm shifters considered for the SHIPBUILDING sector would become mainstream by the year 2030 the latest.
The GREEN RETROFITTING, 3D PRINTING and DRONES appear to have relatively low percentages of likelihood to affect the job situation in Europe (50%, 52% and 55% respectively) as shown in the following figure.

Paradigm shifters (Shipbuilding)		
2019	2025	2030
	<p>Vessel automation, vessel autonomy and advanced robotics</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked 1st with 87%</p> <p>-Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 1st with 79%</p>	
	<p>Digitalization</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked 1st with 87%</p> <p>-Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 2nd with 75%</p>	
	<p>Exploitation of alternative fuels and renewable energy sources</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked 3rd with 83%</p> <p>-Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 3rd with 67%</p>	
	<p>Drones</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked 4th with 73%</p> <p>-Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 4th with 55%</p>	
	<p>Green retrofitting</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked 5th with 70%</p> <p>-Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 6th with 50%</p>	
	<p>3D Printing</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked last with 59%</p> <p>-Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 5th with 52%</p>	

Page 3 - Shipping-Automation 2

⚠ Don't show page if
3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

1) VESSEL AUTOMATION, VESSEL AUTONOMY AND ADVANCED ROBOTICS

(E.G. WELDING AND BLASTING ROBOTS)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

- * 6. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER. PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED. [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Naval architect	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electronics engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine electronics technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electronic equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Welder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boilermaker	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pipe welder (pipe fitter)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sheet metal worker	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Surface treatment operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Abrasive blasting operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mobile crane operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Production plant crane operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Shipwright	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Transport equipment painter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- * 7. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:
 1) Critical thinking and problem solving
 2) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
 3) Communication and collaboration

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT. IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Critical thinking and problem solving		
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 8. THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.
 [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most popular (top) to the least popular (bottom)]

	YES, THIS OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	NO, THIS OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
Innovation management [EXISTING]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Robotics (technician, operator, engineer, repair engineer) [NEW]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Mechatronics (engineer) [EXISTING]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vessel automation (sensor technician, marine automation technician, automation engineer) [NEW]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vessel autonomy (fleet manager, operator, system engineer) [NEW]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cyber-security (officer) [NEW]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 9. FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

	Suitable to all affected occupations	More suitable to affected occupations of technical nature (I.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable to affected occupations other than technical (I.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Life-long learning

Page 4 - Shipping-ALTERNATIVE FUELS 2

Don't show page if

3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

2) EXPLOITATION OF ALTERNATIVE FUELS AND RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES (E.G. LNG, ELECTRIFICATION, FLETTNER ROTORS, ETC.)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 10. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER. PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED. [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Marine engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine engineering drafter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Naval architect	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vessel engine assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 11. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:
1) Flexibility and adaptability
2) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
3) Critical thinking and problem solving

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT. IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Leadership and responsibility

- * 12. THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES. [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most popular (top) to the least popular (bottom)]

	YES, THIS OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	NO, THIS OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
Energy management (planner, infrastructure engineer) [EXISTING]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Alternative fuels (fuel cell engineer) [NEW]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation management [EXISTING]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 13. FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

	Suitable to all affected occupations	More suitable to affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable to affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Life-long learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 5 - Shipping-Digitalization 2

⚠ Don't show page if
 3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 is Offshore Renewable energies

3) DIGITALIZATION (E.G. BIG DATA ANALYTICS, INTERNET OF THINGS APPLICATIONS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, SMART SENSORS, ETC.)
 SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

- * 14. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY

THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER.
 PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED.
 [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Marine engineering drafter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical drafter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electronics engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine engineering drafter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine electronics technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Naval architect	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electronic equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 15.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:

- 1) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
- 2) Creative thinking and innovation
- 3) Critical thinking and problem solving

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT.
 IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 16.THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES).

Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vessel engine assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Computer numerical control (CNC) machine operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Welder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Shipwright	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boilermaker	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pipe welder (pipe fitter)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boat rigger	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 19. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:

- 1) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
- 2) Flexibility and adaptability
- 3) Communication and collaboration

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT. IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 20. THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.

	YES, THIS OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	NO, THIS OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
3D-printing (operator) [EXISTING]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 21. FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

Suitable to all More suitable to More suitable to

Page 11 of 26

disappear

	affected occupations	affected occupations of technical nature (I.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	affected occupations other than technical (I.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Life-long learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 7 - Shipping-Green retrofitting 2

* Don't show page if

3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

5) GREEN RETROFITTING (E.G. SCRUBBER INSTALLATION, BALLAST WATER TREATMENT RETROFITS)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 22.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER. PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED. [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Marine engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Naval architect	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 23.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:

- 1) Flexibility and adaptability
- 2) Knowledge management and transfer
- 3) Critical thinking and problem solving

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT. IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 24. THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.

	YES, THIS OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	NO, THIS OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
Innovation management [EXISTING]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 25. FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

	Suitable to all affected occupations	More suitable to affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable to affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Life-long learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

⚠ Don't show page if

3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Offshore Renewable energies

6) DRONES (FOR VESSEL INSPECTIONS)

SECTOR: SHIPBUILDING

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

- * 26.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER. PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED.
[The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Vessel assembly supervisor	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vessel assembly inspector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marine surveyor	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- * 27.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:
1) Flexibility and adaptability
2) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
3) Critical thinking and problem solving

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT.
IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 28.THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.

YES, THIS NO, THIS

	OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
Innovation management [EXISTING]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 29. FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

	Suitable to all affected occupations	More suitable to affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable to affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Life-long learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- Go to page 10 - Offshore-Automation 1 if
3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding & Offshore Renewable energies
- Else go to thank-you page

Page 9 - Offshore 0

- **Don't show page** if
3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

1st Delphi Round Overview (Offshore Renewable Energy)

From the 1st Delphi round, the majority of the respondents supported that all of the paradigm shifters considered for the OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY sector would become mainstream by the year 2030 the latest. The ENERGY STORAGE and 3D PRINTING appear to have relatively low percentages of likelihood to affect the job situation in Europe (58% and 50% respectively).

Paradigm shifters (Offshore)		
2019	2025	2030
<p>Smart Grid and Smart Sensors</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked 1st with 82% -Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 1st with 70%</p>		
<p>Big Data</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked 2nd with 81% -Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 2nd with 69%</p>		
<p>Energy Storage</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked 2nd with 81% -Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 4th with 58%</p>		
<p>Automation and Advanced Robotics</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked 3rd with 79% -Will affect the job situation? : Ranked 3rd with 67%</p>		
<p>3D Printing</p> <p>-Will become mainstream? : Ranked last with 59% -Will affect the job situation? : Ranked last with 50%</p>		

Page 10 - Offshore-Automation 1

⚠ Don't show page if
 3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 is Shipbuilding

1) AUTOMATION & ADVANCED ROBOTICS (SUCH AS REMOTELY OPERATED

VEHICLES, DRONES, ETC. USED IN SURVEYS, INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS TRANSFER, INSPECTIONS, MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR)
SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 30.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER. PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED.
 [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Cable installer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tidal power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wave power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wind turbine technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Welder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maintenance and repair engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Construction commercial diver	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electronic equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar energy technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hydropower technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 31.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:

- 1) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
- 2) Flexibility and adaptability
- 3) Communication and collaboration

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT.
 IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 32. THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.
 [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most popular (top) to the least popular (bottom)]

	YES, THIS OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	NO, THIS OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
Drone and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) pilot-operator (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Robotics (constructor, programmer, operator) (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Autonomous system operator (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Big Data manager (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Virtual Reality (VR) designer (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Artificial Intelligence (AI) professional (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Predictive maintenance analyst (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cyber security expert (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Mechatronics technician (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sustainability engineer (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 33. FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

	Suitable to all affected occupations	More suitable to affected occupations of technical nature (I.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable to affected occupations other than technical (I.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Life-long learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 11 - Offshore-3D Printing 2

⚠ Don't show page if
3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

2) 3D PRINTING (FOR MASSIVE PRODUCTION OF INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS USED IN CONSTRUCTION AND INSTALLATION, AS WELL AS IN REPAIR)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 34.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER.
PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED.
[The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

	Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Welder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wave power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wind turbine technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tidal power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar energy technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hydropower technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electromechanical engineering technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electronic equipment assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Printed circuit board assembler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 35.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:
1) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
2) Flexibility and adaptability
3) Critical thinking and problem solving

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT.
IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 36. THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.
 [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most popular (top) to the least popular (bottom)]

	YES, THIS OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	NO, THIS OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
3D printing (technician, engineer, expert) (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Designer of parts for 3D printing (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3D printer maintenance worker (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 37. FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

	Suitable to all affected occupations	More suitable to affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable to affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Life-long learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 12 - Offshore-Smart grid 2

* Don't show page if
 3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
 is Shipbuilding

3) SMART GRID & SMART SENSORS (FOR REMOTE OPERATION OF THE OFFSHORE RENEWABLES FARMS, AUTO-INSPECTIONS OF THE INFRASTRUCTURES COMPONENTS, AUTO-REPAIR OF ELECTROMECHANICAL ASPECTS OF THE INFRASTRUCTURES AND EFFICIENT POWER DISTRIBUTION TO THE ELECTRICITY GRID)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

- * 38. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER. PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED. [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

	Re-training will be required	Demand will Increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Power distribution engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electric power generation engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maintenance and repair engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Power production plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar power plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- * 39. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:

- 1) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
- 2) Flexibility and adaptability
- 3) Communication and collaboration

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT. IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 40. THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW.

PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.

[The occupations listed below are sorted from the most popular (top) to the least popular (bottom)]

	YES, THIS OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	NO, THIS OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
Sensors (developer, installer, technician) (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Remote controller (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Big Data analyst (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Artificial Intelligence (AI) professional (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electricity consultant (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 41.FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

	Suitable to all affected occupations	More suitable to affected occupations of technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable to affected occupations other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Life-long learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 13 - Offshore-Big data 2

⚠ Don't show page if
3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

4) BIG DATA (FOR RECORDING AND MANAGING REAL-TIME, OF LARGE AMOUNT DATA, WHICH CAN CONTRIBUTE TO ENERGY SYSTEMS EFFICIENCY OPTIMIZATION, AS WELL AS OPERATIONS' OPTIMIZATION AND PREDICTIONS FOR MAINTENANCE)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

* 42.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY

THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER.
 PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED.
 [The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

	Re-training will be required	Demand will Increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
Renewable energy engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Energy systems engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wind energy engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Power distribution engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Power production plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electric power generation engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maintenance and repair engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wind turbine technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar energy engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar energy technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar power plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hydropower technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wave power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tidal power technician	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- * 43.IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:
- 1) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
 - 2) Flexibility and adaptability
 - 3) Initiative and self-direction

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT.
 IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 44. THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.
[The occupations listed below are sorted from the most popular (top) to the least popular (bottom)]

	YES, THIS OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	NO, THIS OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
Big Data systems (developer, engineer) (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 45. FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

	Suitable to all affected occupations	More suitable to affected occupations of technical nature (I.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	More suitable to affected occupations other than technical (I.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Life-long learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page 14 - Offshore-Energy storage 2

⚠ Don't show page if
3. SECTOR OF YOUR EXPERTISE
is Shipbuilding

5) ENERGY STORAGE (NEW BATTERY TECHNOLOGY, ETC.)

SECTOR: OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY

[PLEASE ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS]

- * 46. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE FOLLOWING EXISTING OCCUPATIONS WOULD BE AFFECTED BY THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER. PLEASE SELECT THE BEST OPTIONS THAT DESCRIBE THE WAY THEY WOULD BE AFFECTED.
[The occupations listed below are sorted from the most affected (top) to the least affected (bottom)]

Re-training will be required	Demand will increase	Demand will decrease	The occupation will disappear
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Power production plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar power plant operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Power distribution engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electric power generation engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maintenance and repair engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- * 47. IT WAS FOUND (FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND) THAT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS THAT THE ADVERSELY AFFECTED WORKFORCE WOULD NEED TO HAVE IN ORDER TO BE EMPLOYABLE IN A DIFFERENT JOB TYPE/SECTOR WOULD BE THE FOLLOWING:
- 1) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy
 - 2) Flexibility and adaptability
 - 3) Communication and collaboration

IF YOU AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE APPROPRIATE OPTION TO DECLARE YOUR AGREEMENT.
IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH THE ABOVE, PLEASE SELECT THE THREE (3) MOST IMPORTANT TRANSFERABLE SKILLS FROM THE LIST BELOW.

	Important skill	I agree with the results of the 1st Delphi round
Creative thinking and Innovation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Critical thinking and problem solving	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication and collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge management and transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) literacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flexibility and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiative and self-direction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Productivity and accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership and responsibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 48. THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE SUBJECT PARADIGM SHIFTER WOULD CAUSE SOME OCCUPATIONS TO EMERGE (I.E. IT WOULD CREATE NEW OCCUPATIONS AND ALSO FAVOUR SOME EXISTING ONES). FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, THE RESPONDENTS SUGGESTED THE OCCUPATION(S) SHOWN BELOW. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTION THAT APPLIES.
[The occupations listed below are sorted from the most popular (top) to the least popular (bottom)]

	YES, THIS OCCUPATION WILL EMERGE	NO, THIS OCCUPATION WILL NOT EMERGE
Energy storage specialist (NEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Material engineer (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Grid Insulation and Construction professional (EXISTING)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * 49. FROM THE 1ST DELPHI ROUND, IT WAS FOUND THAT THE FOLLOWING EDUCATIONAL METHODS WOULD PROVIDE TO THE WORKFORCE THE NEW REQUIRED SKILLS MORE EFFECTIVELY. PLEASE SELECT THE OPTIONS THAT APPLY.

Suitable to all affected occupations More suitable to affected occupations of More suitable to affected occupations

	technical nature (i.e. engineers, technicians etc.)	other than technical (i.e. managers, supervisors etc.)
Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the job training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation driven vocational training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher education new technology courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Educational programs with industry placements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blended apprenticeships (on-site and in-class including cross-country mobility)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vocational training courses agreed with the workforce, their unions and employers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Webinars combined with training on the job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online courses on new technologies (i.e. Artificial Intelligence (AI) , Augmented reality, 3D applications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Life-long learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Your responses have been registered!

Thank you for taking the time to complete the survey, your input is valuable to us. Obtaining information from organisations such as yours will provide the project team with the necessary information required in order to ensure the highest level of quality for the MATES deliverables.

Once MATES receives all the responses from round one, the results will be analysed and you may be contacted again with a second round of questions in order to achieve a clear group consensus on the relevant trends and paradigm shifters.

We really appreciate your efforts and we are confident that the information provided will be effectively used for the MATES project.

Many thanks

The MATES Project Team

